

THE EFFECT OF PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL ON EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION IN MEDIA AND ENTERTAINMENT SECTOR IN KERALA

REPORT SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR
POST DOCTORAL FELLOW PROGRAMME (PDF) IN COMMERCE
UNDER THE FACULTY OF COMMERCE
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
SRINIVAS NAGAR, MUKKA, MANGALORE, KARNATAKA

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DECLARATION

I, **Dr. Sujith AS**, do hereby declare that this Report entitled “**THE EFFECT OF PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL ON EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION IN MEDIA AND ENTERTAINMENT SECTOR IN KERALA**” submitted by me for the Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Post-Doctoral Fellow Programme (PDF) in Commerce is the record of original and independent research work done by me under the supervision and guidance of **Dr.P.S. Aithal**, Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India. I further declare that this thesis has not previously formed the basis for the award of any Degree, Diploma, or other similar titles or recognition in any University.

Mangalore
27 September, 2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the Report entitled “**THE EFFECT OF PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL ON EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION IN MEDIA AND ENTERTAINMENT SECTOR IN KERALA**” submitted to Srinivas University, Mangalore, for the Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Post-Doctoral Fellow Programme (PDF) in Commerce is an authentic record of bonafide research carried out by **Dr. Sujith A S**, under my guidance and supervision and that it has not been previously submitted for any degree or diploma, or other similar title or recognition in any University.

He is permitted to submit the Report to the University.

Mangalore
September, 2022

Dr. P. S. AITHAL

Report forwarded to the Srinivas University, Mangalore

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost, I am deeply grateful for the continuous support, insight and patience of my supervisors, **Dr. P. S. Aithal**, Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore: without their constant trust and support, this Report would not have been completed.

I would like to acknowledge all the teachers who has taught and guided me from since my childhood. I would not have been able to accomplish this task without their blessing and support.

I am incredibly grateful to my family members, friends, colleagues, and well-wishers for their love, concern, prayer, care, ample support and prayers.

Besides all this, several people have knowingly and unknowingly helped me in the successful accomplishment of this research work. Thanks to one and all.

Dr. SUJITH A S

**To
My Teachers**

ABSTRACT

Employee Performance Appraisal(PA) is a method used to evaluate the performance of individual employees within an organisation against a predetermined set of criteria and, in turn, the organization's overall performance. This method increases the productivity of employees. In the past year, all types of organisations have utilised performance appraisal systems effectively as a development tool. Different methods are used to evaluate the performance of employees. Traditional methods of performance appraisal include Confidential report, Critical incidents, check list method, Straight ranking method, Factor comparison technique, etc. Modern methods of PA include Management By Objectives (MBO), Assessment Centres, 360 Degree PA, Behaviourally Anchored Rating Scale, etc.

The study was conducted in media and entertainment sector in Kerala titled “The Effect of PA on Employee Motivation in Media and Entertainment Sector in Kerala”. The companies in each sector were selected randomly. Survey method was used to collect primary data.

Both the primary and the secondary data were used for the study. The primary data were obtained using a six-part questionnaire. Respondents were asked to react on their role as a ratee in the PA system referred to by the organisations. Part I of the questionnaire contained demographic questions, Part II contained question used to understand the general nature of the PA system. Part III of the questionnaire used to find out the fairness level of PA. Part IV incorporated questions used to understand the feedback mechanism of the PA. Part V included the questions, helps to understand the use of PA results. Part III of the questionnaire used to know the effect of PA on employee motivation.

Books,committee reports, magazines, government publications, official records, the Internet, and other sources provided the secondary data. The acquired data were correctly categorised and evaluated with the study's purposes in mind.

The study revealed that PA is an effective device for improving organisational effectiveness. The result shows that PA has a significant role in the process of employees' motivation. So in this study, it is clear that PA effected positively as a tool for employee motivation.

Keywords: PA system, PA impact, PA fairness, PA results, PA feedback, Employee motivation

CONTENTS

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

Sl. No.	Contents	Page No.
1.1	Introduction to Performance Appraisal	1
1.2	The concept of Performance Appraisal	2
1.3	Performance Appraisal and Motivation	3
1.4	Application of Motivational theories in Business	4
1.5	Equity Theory of Motivation	5
1.6	Expectancy Theory of Motivation	7
1.7	Salient features of the Media and entertainment sector	8
	1.7.1 The first steps	8
	1.7.2 Accepting the Role of Television	8
	1.7.3 Globalisation & private TV channels	9
	1.7.4 Establishing TRAI & giving industry status to M&E	9
	1.7.5 The digital dominance	9
	1.7.6 Climbing new heights	9
1.8	Problem of the study	10
1.9	Significance of the study	10
1.10	Scope of the study	11
1.11	Objectives of the Study	11
1.12	Hypotheses of the study	11
1.13	Methodology	12
	1.13.1 Data collection procedures	12
	1.13.2 Instrumentation	12
	1.13.3 Pilot study and checking the Reliability	13
	1.13.4 Data processing and analysis	13
	1.13.5 Universe of the study	14
1.14	Limitations of the study	14
1.15	Scheme of Presentation of Report	14
	References	

CHAPTER 2

A general review of research and literature

Sl. No.	Contents	Page No.
2.1	Introduction	18
2.2	Performance Appraisal	18
2.3	Employee's Performance	19
2.4	Fairness of performance Appraisal Systems	20
2.5	Performance Appraisal feedback	20
2.6	Uses of Performance Appraisal Results	21
2.7	Motivation	22
2.8	Performance Appraisal and Employee Motivation	23
	References	

CHAPTER 3
The Conceptual framework

Sl. No.	Contents	Page No.
3.1	Equity Theory	29
3.2	Equity Theory of Motivation	30
3.3	Functionality of Equity Theory of Motivation	31
3.4	Common Inputs & Outputs affects Equity	32
3.5	Inputs that Affect Equity & Motivation	32
3.6	Outputs that Affect Equity & Motivation	33
3.7	The Optimal Ratio of Equity for Motivation	33
3.8	The Equity Theory of Motivation in Business	34
3.9	The Equity Theory of Motivation for Personal Use	34
3.10	Assumptions of the Equity Theory of Motivation	35
3.11	Expectancy theory	35
3.12	Elements of expectancy theory	36
3.13	Application of expectancy theory	37
3.14	Advantages of expectancy theory and the corresponding organisational impact	38
3.15	Limitation of expectancy theory	38
3.16	Equity verses Expectancy	39
2.17	Conceptual Framework	40
3.18	Research Hypothesis	41
	References	

CHAPTER 4
Analysis and Interpretation

Sl. No.	Contents	Page No.
4.1	Introduction	44
4.2	Data exploration	44
	4.2.1 Missing Values and Outliers	45
	4.2.2 Normally Distributed Data	46
	4.2.3 Independent Responses	47
4.3	Preliminary Data Analysis	48
	4.3.1 Demographics	48
	4.3.2 Statistics related to performance appraisal in general	49
	4.3.3 Statistics related to fairness of performance appraisal system	50
	4.3.4 Statistics related to feedback of performance appraisal	53
	4.3.5 Statistics related to use of performance appraisal results	54
	4.3.6 Statistics related to effect of performance appraisal on motivation	55
4.4	e Proposed Research Model	56
4.5	Confirmatory Factor Analysis	56
4.6	Reliability analysis	60
4.7	Validity Analysis	62
4.8	Hypotheses Testing	63

CHAPTER 5

Summary of findings and policy recommendations

Sl. No.	Contents	Page No.
5.1	Summary of findings	68
5.2	Conclusion	70
5.3	Policy recommendations	71
5.4	Future enactment	72

Appendix

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Name of Table	Page No.
4.1	Statistics of Normality Test of the Data	47
4.2	Summary of the Demographic Characteristics of Respondents	48
4.3	Summary of the statistics related to performance appraisal policy	49
4.4	Summary of the statistics related to effective and efficient administration of performance appraisal policy by the management	49
4.5	Summary of the statistics related to policy shared with staff	50
4.6	Summary of the statistics related to appraised any staff	50
4.7	Summary of the statistics related to training on Performance Appraisal in the organization	50
4.8	Summary of the statistics related to fairness of performance appraisal system	50
4.9	Summary of the statistics related to PA form used by employees at the same grade/group	51
4.10	Summary of the statistics related to appraised done	51
4.11	Summary of the statistics related to conduction of appraisal	51
4.12	Summary of the statistics related to pre-determined objectives against which you were evaluated	52
4.13	Summary of the statistics related to determination the objectives	52
4.14	Summary of the statistics related to frequency of appraised	52
4.15	Summary of the statistics related to PA fairly conducted	53
4.16	Summary of the statistics related to motivation by PA	53
4.17	Summary of the statistics related to getting feedback after appraisal	53
4.18	Summary of the statistics related to feedback reflected performance	53
4.19	Summary of the statistics related to feedback received motivate them	54
4.20	Summary of the statistics related to organization use performance appraisal	54
4.21	Summary of the statistics related to use of performance appraisal	54
4.22	Summary of the statistics related to use of performance appraisal is sufficient	55
4.23	Summary of the statistics related to effect of performance appraisal on motivation	55
4.24	Model Fitness Criteria	57
4.25	Summary of the Model Fit Indices for the Structural Model (SEM)	60
4.26	Reliability Analysis Pertaining to Variables	61
4.27	Measurement model output-CFA	63
4.28	Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	64
4.29	Table showing the Square Root of AVE and Correlation Coefficient Values	64
4.30	SEM results	65
4.31	Model summary (H2)	65
4.32	ANOVA	66
4.33	Regression	66
4.34	Model summary (H3)	66
4.35	ANOVA	66
4.36	Regression	66
4.37	Model summary (H4)	67
4.38	ANOVA	67
4.39	Regression	67

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure No.	Name of Figures	Page No.
3.1	Expectancy Theory Model	37
3.2	PA and Employee Motivation Model	41
4.1	Research Model	56
4.2	SEM output	65

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Expansion
PA	Performance Appraisal
PAS	Performance Appraisal System
BARS	Behaviourally Anchored Rating Scale
BPM	Business Process Management
HR	Human Resource
HRD	Human Resource Development
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
TRAI	The Telecom Regulatory Authority of India
AVGC	The Animation, Visual Effects, Gaming and Comic
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction to Performance Appraisal

The most important element of a performance management system is performance appraisal (PA) also called performance review. PA is the process of setting standards, assessing employee performance against the set standards, giving employee feedback on their performance and making plans for performance improvement (Byars & Rue, 2000)[1]. This exercise is usually conducted on regular basis-six months to one year but the period can vary depending on the purpose (Greenhaus et al., 1990)[2]. Many organizations have accepted PA as an instrument for measuring and managing employee performance (Murphy & Cleveland, 1991) [3]. Boxall and Purcell (2003)[4] have opined that the objective of PA is not only to measure and manage employee performance but to integrate it to the organization's overall goals. According to Longenecker and Goff (1992) [5], many managers and human resource practitioners have embraced PA because they believe it has influenced performance of workers in a good way.

Most of the organizations are conducting PA for the evaluation of their employees in recent times. One of the major competitive and dynamic sectors is media and entertainment sector. It is a vibrant sector in the service sector in Kerala. PA is an important tool to evaluate the performance of employees thereby enhancing the overall performance of the organization. So each and every organizations conducting PA for various purposes. PA is also affect the level of motivation of employees. In this context, this study tries to find out impact of performance appraisal on employee motivation.

This study's main goal was to investigate how PA affected employee motivation in Kerala's media and entertainment industry. The study was motivated by the following specific goals: to ascertain how much employees in the media and entertainment sector believe the PA system is fair; to ascertain whether employees in this sector receive clear feedback on PA; to ascertain how feedback from the PA process is used to motivate employees; and to ascertain how management can enhance the appraisal process to motivate employees.

From media and entertainment sector, Visual media will be considering for the study. Under this the top two Malayalam news channels are considered for this study, ie, Twenty Four

News and Malayala Manorama. Stratified random sampling will be used for sample selection and questionnaire is used to collect primary data.

1.2 The concept of Performance Appraisal

Performance appraisals are an essential part of human resource management that has a big impact on employee and organisational effectiveness. Therefore, it is essential for businesses to continuously evaluate employee performance through Performance Appraisal (PA).

Performance appraisal is now one of the most crucial parts of human resource practises. They are strategic in nature and help the organisation get the most benefits by integrating with its policies. Over the course of more than a century, the idea of performance evaluation has developed from various theories of motivation, including Abraham Maslow's "hierarchy of needs," Herzberg's "two factor theory," Vroom's "expectancy theory," Patton's "managerial motivators," Locke's "goal setting theory," McClelland's "achievement theory," etc. Performance evaluation, according to Lusier & Hendon (2015) [6], is the ongoing practise of assessing employee performance. Reviewing an employee's performance over time is what it is. It only constitutes one element of performance management.

The issue of performance appraisal is understood to involve a variety of tasks (Fletcher, 2001) [7]. Performance appraisals should be used as a tool for staff development, according to Cascio (1991) [8]. Similar to this, according to Cardy & Dobbins (1994) [9], "performance appraisal should be more than just a historical evaluation. Additionally, it ought to emphasise the ratees' ability level and the future. These actions in human resources might be viewed as developmental because of the connection between performance assessment and training. Training comes after a performance review naturally. The results of the evaluation of an employee's work should be used to guide training. One of the topics that has received a great deal of attention in the psychology of work is performance evaluation (Kuvaas, 2006) [10].

The performance appraisal system has evolved through time, beginning with personality-based appraisal systems in the 1950s and goal-setting and performance-based skills in the 1960s. It has since become a crucial tool for managing employees and businesses as a whole. A generation ago, employee traits, weaknesses, and skills were often highlighted in performance appraisal systems; however, modern appraisal philosophy places a greater emphasis on current performance and long-term objectives. The emphasis on employee involvement in creating goals with the supervisor in accordance with contemporary thinking. Modern appraisal methods typically place a strong emphasis on a number of goals, like as

- Improvement in the communication between supervisors and subordinates through the use of feedback between them.
- Identification of the scope for performance improvement and means to achieve this.
- Identification of individual training and development needs.
- Identification of the potential of individuals for promotion, placement, etc.
- As the basis for remuneration and reward, on the basis of performance.
- As a powerful means of managerial control, through the setting of objectives and a review of success or failure in achieving those. (Edmonstone,1996 [11]; Longenecker, 1997) [12].

Research as well as organisational experience has shown that performance rating systems need two essential elements in order to accomplish these broad objectives. They must first have a reliable rating system in place. In other words, the organisation must have a system in place to monitor compliance and retain assessment data, as well as a clearly defined rating process or procedures, a suitable user-friendly instrument (form), and. The manager who is really tasked with evaluating employee performance is the second crucial element of an effective performance appraisal system. The manager must possess the knowledge and drive necessary to carry out efficient performance reviews when given the difficult position of "rater" of performance (Fink & Lingenecker, 1998) [13].

Despite being widely used, the formal performance review process nevertheless faces a lot of scrutiny and criticism. One of the most extensively studied topics in individual and organisational psychology is performance evaluation (Murphy & Cleveland, 1995) [14]. In an effort to increase the process' accuracy and perceived fairness, researchers have created and practitioners have put into practise a variety of modifications to the evaluation criteria, rating instruments, and appraisal methods (Banks & Murphy, 1985) [15]. Nevertheless, despite the focus and money devoted to the practise, employee unhappiness with the procedures persists, and systems are frequently seen as unreliable and unjust.

1.3 Performance Appraisal and Motivation

Performances Appraisal definitely evaluate employees' performance and offer some support in helping them develop goals, identify their destinations and future, and ultimately reach their objectives. Various studies defined motivation as the desire to take action that was shaped by doing something or having the ability to meet a few demands (Judge., et al., 2002) [16]. These businesses recognised the importance of motivating their workforce to achieve

the objectives of the company (Schulze & Steyn, 2003) [17]. The convinced personnel identify with the behaviour and provide fulfilment and dedication that are relied upon to improve the character of work and comply with the businesses' strategies that will generally emerge as more efficient (Benabou & Tirole, 2003) [18]. By making the work more interesting and relevant, keeping the people more employed, and improving their work performance, motivation increases the contribution of the occupation (Steers, et al., 2004) [19].

To meet the company goals, employee motivation is crucial, critical, and significant employee attributes are evaluated (Wang & Guthrie, 2004) [20]. The scientists agree that increasing employee motivation is crucial for improving an organization's output. It speaks to the complex forces and requirements that give someone the energy to do a particular task (Mizuno, et.al. 2006) [21]. Employee motivation is also an essential component of professional operations since it enhances performance and efficiency. High motivation harmonises with professional satisfaction, a sense of pride in one's own job, and a profound sense of commitment to the business (Davis, M, et.al., 2006) [22]. Similar to individuals, corporations can benefit from this element by evaluating the performance of their staff. The research showed that the methods used to evaluate employees, their motives, and finally their performance is all related in exactly the same way. According to the literature, there is a direct correlation between how employees are evaluated, their motives, and finally their performance (Arbaiy & Suradi, 2007) [23].

According to the pertinent literature, performance appraisal studied staffing, training, rewarding, and inspiration standards are four crucial tactics for ensuring proper management of an organization's human resources (Robbins & Coulter, 2011) [24]. Additionally, the development of a performance appraisal method affects staffing, training, and progression. In this manner, the performance review should be used to provide information on which these arrangements can be put together. A performance appraisal system can improve representative performance and benefit employees (Simmons & Lovegrove, 2017) [25].

1.4 Application of Motivational theories in Business

Ramlall (2004) [26] defined motivation as the elements and causes that drive workers to exert extra effort in a particular way in order to attain the desired goals. Nowadays, a company's personnel is both a key component of success and a source of competitive advantage. The purpose of HRM is to ensure that employees are happy, have the necessary knowledge and abilities, and have objectives that motivate them to accomplish their jobs (Borowski & Daya,

2014) [27]. According to the motivational literature we've researched, there are primarily two types of motivational tools: financial and non-financial. Scholars have developed a wide range of theories and models to better understand the elements and circumstances that motivate workers. These ideas and models are divided by academics into two categories: content theories and process theories. First, the content theories essentially assert that internal requirements of employees, such as the fundamental desire for safety, socialisation, esteem, and so forth, motivate people to work hard to satisfy these wants (Borowski & Daya, 2014) [28]. The main issue with content theories, according to Davis and Newstrom (1993) [29], is that it is difficult for managers to observe and ascertain the demands of employees for monitoring purposes. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, Alderfer's ERG Theory, Herzberg's Motivator Hygiene Theory, and McClelland's Learned Needs or Three-Needs Theory are some important content theories of motivation. Second, the process theories that focus on the decision-making process include encouraging employees to adopt particular behaviours and objectives. There are four main process theories of motivation: Expectancy Theory, Equity Theory, Goal-Setting Theory, and Reinforcement Theory. Scholars have concluded that a number of important aspects affect motivation at work based on several motivation theories and investigations. In their research on the Vroom Theory of Expectancy, Lloyd et al. (2016) [30] and Parijat and Bagga (2014) [31] discovered that Vroom highlighted a number of crucial aspects that influence motivation, which improves motivation and job performance. These aspects include the work environment, teamwork, job differentiation, and content, as well as the managers or supervisors who are in charge of evaluating performance and offering candid feedback. Finally, rewards and incentives round out the list. Through the goalsetting theory of motivation, Lunenburg (2011) [32] also identified important aspects that have an impact on motivation. The first component is the deadline, which has a direct impact on the efficacy of the goal since it gives employees a specific aim to reach in a set amount of time. Second, the author claimed that learning goals will lead to better performance than performance goals. This indicates that people like to set goals that will help them develop and use their competences and skills.

1.5 Equity Theory of Motivation

According to the equity theory, people are driven by a desire for justice, and if they notice unfairness in the ratios of their input to output compared to that of their referent group, they will try to make adjustments to their input to bring those ratios into line with what they perceive as fairness (Adams, 1963) [33]. This suggests that workers would be content and

even willing to enhance their work if they saw their toil, expertise, and everything else they provide to the company being fairly compensated by their pay, bonuses, and expressions of gratitude in the form of rewards. It also means that if an employee disagrees with the level of output they are receiving in comparison to the input they provide, they will probably reduce their input in order to achieve parity with the result they are receiving.

Selvarajan and Cloninger (2012) [34] examined the relationship between performance appraisal characteristics (appraisal source, appraisal purpose, and feedback richness) and perceived employee reactions to the appraisal characteristics (perceived fairness and perceived accuracy of appraisals), as well as the outcomes of the appraisals, in a study on Mexican employees (appraisal satisfaction and motivation to improve). The study's findings demonstrated a strong relationship between fair performance reviews and employees' motivation and job happiness. Additionally, in contrast to what Kampkotter (2016) [35] observed in his study, which claimed that employees are driven by performance reviews that are only related to monetary results, employees chose respect and dignity above awards that take the shape of non-monetary outcomes. Because of their culture or history, which places a great value on respect for others, Mexican employees may be the only ones to experience these results. As a result, the type of appraisal resulting rewards may differ based on the people's culture (Selvarajan & Cloninger, 2012) [36]. According to a related study by Cosier and Dalton (1983) [37], the equity theory demonstrates a reversal response to injustice, where it is suggested that an employee who feels like they are not being treated equally as other employees may reduce their inputs. The exact opposite, though, may happen, where the person would work more to win favour, especially if their work was of dubious quality. Adams (1963) [38] suggested that people are driven by how fairly they see equity, which is in direct opposition to what has been observed.

However, this outcome might be a response to deliberate injustice in the workplace. It varies from person to person since some people can take advantage of unfavourable remarks by using them as a source of inspiration to prove the unfavourable person wrong. This backs up Kuvaas' (2006) [39] theory of motivation, according to which an individual may be able to influence and manage an employee's motivation. The expectancy theory of motivation, which holds that employees are motivated when they behave in accordance with expectations and are rewarded in accordance with what they anticipate being given in exchange for their contributions, is another example of the idea that an employee's motivation could be controlled.

1.6 Expectancy Theory of Motivation

According to the expectation theory, workers are driven to put in more effort when they feel that their efforts will result in higher performance, and that improved performance will be recognised by their organisation or firm in a way that is useful to them (Vroom & Deci, 1983) [40] After setting expectations for his or her performance and the incentive that comes with it, an employee will change their inputs to meet those expectations and will anticipate receiving a reward after they have been met. According to the hypothesis, motivation in the workplace will rise if employees sense a strong link between their efforts and their results. The theory argues that there are various sets of goals that employees may have, and they may be motivated if they think:

- There is a positive correlation between efforts and performance,
- Good performances will result in a receiving an expected reward,
- The reward will satisfy a need of importance to the individual,
- The drive to satisfy the need is strong enough to make the effort worthwhile.

Valence

Here, Valence refers to a person's emotional response to a situation's outcome (rewards). It can also be defined as the degree to which an employee wants extrinsic (cash, benefits, promotions, time off) or intrinsic (satisfaction-based) rewards.

Expectancy

The expectations and levels of confidence that employees have in their abilities vary. Management must determine what tools, instruction, or oversight personnel require to remain motivated

Instrumentality

This has to do with how employees believe they will be treated, even if management has made promises to that effect. According to Vroom, an employee acts in ways that offer pleasure and avoid misery as a result of the psychological interaction between their expectations, instrumentality, and values.

Lawler and Suttle (1973) [41] demonstrated the ability of expectancy beliefs to predict behaviour, but they did not demonstrate the validity of many of the theory's more intricate predictions. Similar research by Reinharth and Wahba (1975) [42] revealed that only a very small subset of human behaviour could, at best, be explained by the theory. In circumstances where the individual can clearly perceive the contingencies between acts and outcomes and between first-level and second-level outcomes, the theory based on rationality is useful as a

predictor, whereas ambiguous circumstances force the individual to develop a choice mechanism not based on the expectancy variables (Lawler & Suttle, 1973) [43].

The employee's perceived outcome does not always come to pass since managers and supervisors moderate these perceived outcomes. According to the expectation theory, this could result in a decline in an employee's motivation, particularly if the individual is denied his or her expected outcomes despite changing their inputs to get better results.

1.7 Salient features of the Media and entertainment sector

The fourth pillar of democracy, the media, is one of the most important aspects of any country. It has the power to shape public opinion, spread information, and entertain the masses. Even before independence, India had a rich background when it came to the media and entertainment industry: the first printing press was set up in 1674 and radio & broadcasting began in 1923. Post-independence, the sector saw monumental growth, especially after the television came in 1959. Today, it is one of the strongest and sunrise sectors, contributing immensely to the Indian economy. As India enters the 75th year of its being, here's looking at the key events and policies that shaped the Indian media and entertainment industry since independence.

1.7.1 The first steps

It was more of a priority in the first few years after independence to streamline pre-existing media channels and introduce regulatory acts. The print industry benefited greatly from the passage of landmark legislation such as the Cinematograph Act of 1952, which regulated the grading and certification of motion pictures, and The Copyright Act of 1957, which established the country's first modern Intellectual Property Regime. There have been six updates to the law since it was initially passed.

The media and entertainment industries in India have a strong cultural foundation thanks to the efforts of former Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru, who oversaw the establishment of the Lalit Kala, Sangeet Natak, and Sahitya academies and the expansion of the All India Radio (AIR).

1.7.2 Accepting the Role of Television

In 1959, an experimental broadcast was broadcast from a makeshift studio in Delhi using a tiny transmitter, marking the beginning of the television industry. Only in 1965 did regular broadcasts start, and by 1975, only seven Indian cities even had television reception. Cult classics such as the Ramayana and the Mahabharata first appeared on Doordarshan's small

screens in the 1980s. By 1982, people in India were able to watch TV with coloured broadcasts.

It was also in the early 1980s that the first paid television commercials appeared, with Gwalior Suitings as possibly the first advertiser. It is believed that Bombay Dyeing aired the first colour television commercial around this time.

1.7.3 Globalisation & private TV channels

Indian broadcasting benefited greatly from the country's liberalisation of trade in the early 1990s, when globalisation began. This country's first private television network, Zee TV, debuted in October 1992. Then a slew of music, movie, entertainment, infotainment, animation, and news-specific TV shows emerged.

The television industry received a significant boost as the Indian market became more accessible to foreign companies, in large part due to the efforts of advertisers. Iconic advertisements were provided by companies like Amul, Archies, Pidilite, Nestle, etc.

By issuing guidelines, policies, regulations, and broadcasting licences, the Prasar Bharti Act of 1990 and the Cable Networks Act of 1995 provided the sector with more structure.

1.7.4 Establishing TRAI & giving industry status to M&E

The Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI) was founded in 1997 as a broadcasting regulator during the administration of Atal Bihari Vajpayee. Additionally, he legitimised the M&E market so that it could access institutional financing from financial institutions. In the years following the intervention, the film and entertainment industry's exports grew by enormous proportions.

His administration also liberalised policies regarding foreign investment in news and current affairs, allowing for 26% of private channels and 100% of privatised radio stations to accept funding from abroad. Allowing foreign direct investment sparked expansion in the print media industry.

1.7.5 The digital dominance

As the world transitioned into the new millennium, the media and entertainment industry benefited from the widespread adoption of new technologies like smartphones and the internet. For this reason, the fields of content production, SEO, and online advertising have experienced exponential growth over the past two decades.

As OTT services and creators of user-generated content become more pervasive across multiple social media platforms, the market is opening up to possibilities never before seen.

1.7.6 Climbing new heights

The media and entertainment industry has been striving for new heights in recent years, helped in part by increased government regulation and support. While there are still important issues to resolve in regards to press freedom and data privacy, steps have been taken to improve the industry as a whole. These steps include the development of a new national film policy to boost the animation industry, the exclusion of the entertainment tax from the Goods and Services Tax, the revision of foreign direct investment guidelines, and the enhancement of artists' rights to collect royalties. Government support for the AVGC industry will bring with it a whole new set of possibilities.

It's also worth noting that self-regulatory norms set by organisations like ASCI, IAMAI, etc. are constantly being updated to reflect the new digitally-led world.

The I&B Ministry predicts that the media and entertainment industry will grow to be worth \$100 billion (7.5 lakh crore) by 2030. By 2025, analysts predict that it will generate annual revenue of Rs 4 lakh crore lakh rupees.

1.8 Problem of the study

PA is a vital and indispensable human resource management tool. According to Murphy and Cleveland (1995) [44], if properly used PA has many potential advantages such as deciding the remuneration, advancements, downgrading and allocations of employees. PAs are important in providing directions for career paths through the managers which may improve employee obligation and fulfillment in the organization. PA is also used to take stock of the skills and knowledge of employees and it communicates and appreciate level of performance to employees (Walsh& Fisher, 2006) [45].

PA is also considering as a tool for employee motivation. But sometimes it affects adversely. As vibrant sector conducting a systematic employee performance system, media and entertainment sector is selected for this study. Each organizations conducting their methods of appraisal differently and the most of the organizations conducting their appraisal annually. Different studies conducted in the field of performance appraisal, but this study exclusively tries to find out the effect of performance appraisal on motivation in media and entertainment sector in Kerala.

1.9 Significance of the study

Evaluation of staff performance is essential in any company. It's also useful for boosting morale in the workplace. It will also aid in figuring out whether or not the evaluation's results

can be put to good use. The results will show management whether or not this procedure is useful to the employees' day-to-day work. The results of this investigation into the lapses can be used to boost employee morale and output.

The findings of this study will also be useful in informing stakeholders and policymakers about how to assess and improve worker motivation. The findings will aid in the development of strategic plans for encouraging and retaining top talent in government.

Knowledge about performance evaluation and employee motivation in Kerala's media and entertainment industries will be enhanced and expanded thanks to the study's findings. This study will be referenced by future researchers, and its findings and recommendations can be examined in depth by other groups.

1.10 Scope of the study

This research is conducted within the geographical boundary of Kerala and selected three organisations for the study, i.e. Twenty Fours news and Malayala Manrama.

1.11 Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of this study are:

- [1] To determine the extent to which employees in media and entertainment sector perceive the performance appraisal system as fair.
- [2] To establish whether employees in media and entertainment sector receive clear feedback on their performance appraisal.
- [3] To determine how performance appraisal results are used to motivate employees of in media and entertainment sector.
- [4] To establish how the management of media and entertainment sector can improve their performance appraisal process to motivate employees.

1.12 Hypotheses of the study

The study was guided by the following hypotheses:

- [1] H1: There is a significant impact of performance appraisal on employee motivation
- [2] H2. There is a significant impact of fairness of performance appraisal system
- [3] H3. There is a significant impact of feedback on performance appraisal
- [4] H4. There is a significant impact of use of performance appraisal results

1.13 Methodology

For the purpose of data collection Census method is adopted as the size of population is comparatively smaller. The questionnaires were distributed to all the permanent employees of both Twenty Four News and Manaroma News who are having an experience at the channel for more than one year. A total of 392 questionnaires were distributed, 190 questionnaires at Manaroma News and 202 at Twenty Four News out of which 250 were duly filled and returned. Therefore, the final size of population for the study was 250.

1.13.1 Data collection procedures

The study is both descriptive and analytical in character, and therefore both the primary and secondary data have been used for the study.

Primary data for the study have been collected from 543 sample respondents of 30 selected service sector organisations spread across the state of Kerala. The sample units have been selected by purposive sampling method and the sample respondents according to the simple random sampling method.

The secondary data have comparatively got only a very limited importance as far as the execution of the present study is concerned. A review of the published literature in the form of books, periodicals and these in the area of PA in particular, and, Human Resource Management in general, have benefited from understanding the present scenario. Various PA forms and review reports have also been examined.

1.13.2 Instrumentation

A survey instrument was used to collect data in this study from eligible employees who were defined as operational, technical and managerial staff and required to participate in the employee PA system. All participants were asked to respond to their role as a ratee.

Part I of the questionnaire included a short demographic questionnaire. Part II of the questionnaire included questions used to understand the organisation's PA system in a general manner. Part III of the questionnaire used to measure the fairness of PA. Part IV of the questionnaire comprised measures the functioning of performance appraisal feedback. Part V of the questionnaire was used to understand the uses of PA results. Finally Part VI used to measure the Effect of PA on Employee Motivation in media and entertainment sector in Kerala.

1.13.4 Pilot study and checking the Reliability

Essential pilot studies have been carried out at the beginning stage of the research study. Reliability of the questionnaire has been duly checked through executing it to 20 respondents each from two sample units at the time of the pilot study. The very procedures have been repeated among the identical respondents as part of the study after a gap of six months and reliability in their response has been found very high.

1.13.5 Data processing and analysis

Data analysis and interpretation is the process in which meaning is assigned to the information gathered and meaningful insights are found. Data integrity is needed for accurate and suitable analysis in accordance with Resnik & Shampoo (2009) [46]. Improper statistical analysis leads to mislead results (Shepard, 2002) [47] and directly influences research perception of researchers. This chapter consists of seven sections. Throughout the work, the first part deals with data exploration, in the second part the preliminary data analysis is presented, third part deals with exploratory factor analysis, fourth part present research model, the fifth part discuss confirmative factor analyses, sixth part deals with reliability analysis, seventh-part deals with validity analysis and eight-part, structural equation modelling is presented.

The first phase of data analysis includes data exploration that usually comprises the features of a dataset. During the data exploration, the researcher knows about the number of cases and variables inside the data set. This even helps to identify the lack of observations with designs since they have a powerful impact on the parameters of the model being tested.

The preliminary data analysis was done with the help of SPSS 23.0 and “Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM).” Results are presented in terms of reliability, validity of tool and the descriptive analysis in the context of demographic findings. The fifth, sixth, seventh and eight part of this chapter consists of the analysis done with the help of PLS-SEM. PLS-SEM was used to apply Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). CFA was used to verify the factor structure of a set of observed variables.

SEM was used to examine the relationship between the independent and dependent factors considered in the conceptual model.

1.13.6 Universe of the study

The universe of the present study extends to the service sector in the whole state of Kerala. Based on the statistical analysis of the data, the conclusions are drawn, and the policy recommendations made after that are applicable throughout the service sector of Kerala. Twenty Four news and Manrama News were selected for the study. The total number of employees under study is 392.(190+202)

1.14 Limitations of the study

The researcher will face some limitations in terms of the willingness of the employees in the organisation. Several members of staff are unwilling to fully cooperate as they felt that the study is interfering with their busy schedules and an additional work to them. Employees are not willing to give information voluntarily and especially information that touched on them and their supervisors for fear of victimization. The employees are busy in their routine work schedules so the workers may not agree to respond to the questionnaire. Some others will agree to respond the questionnaire, but their responses may indifferent and inconsistent.

1.15 Scheme of Presentation of Report

Chapter 1: Introduction

Chapter 2: Literature Review

Chapter 3: Conceptual Framework

Chapter 4: Data analysis and Interpretation

Chapter 5: Findings and Suggestions

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CHAPTER TWO

A GENERAL REVIEW OF RESEARCH AND LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

This chapter reviews the existing literature on the research subject. The chapter will be divided into the following sections: Performance Appraisal; Employee's Performance; fairness of PA system; Uses of PA; PA feedback; Motivation and the relationship between PA and employee motivation.

2.2 Performance Appraisal

Cleveland, Murphy & Williams, (1989) [1] Human resource decisions, evaluation, and feedback are just a few of the uses for performance appraisal systems.

Zavvarzadeh & Mahrpkh (1997) [2] many difficulties in the midst for recruits to confirm organisation apprehension be straight for the effects of the manager's failure to analyses course of action. Solving a variety of work-related issues, including job assignment, promotion, relocation, removal from office, training, and remuneration, in reality due to a lack of judgement structure.

Martin (1998)[3] "Performance management systems are frequently included in performance appraisals. Performance management systems coordinate and manage all aspects of an organization's resources in order to obtain the best results possible.

Nasud (1999)[4] the appraisal system is an excellent instrument for determining the worth and magnitude of manpower performance. Performance evaluation is now widely recognised as a critical component of human resource management and a component of the management control process.

Williams (2002)[5] Performance management entails deciding the strategic aim, establishing team goals, developing a performance plan, analysing performance (using an appraisal system), identifying development needs, and assigning rewards.

Ruddin (2005)[6] Although performance appraisal appears to be straightforward, studies show that it is widely employed in performance feedback and identifying individual employee strengths and weaknesses.

Talya and Berim (2010)[7] Different companies use performance appraisal systems to

reward their employees in the form of bonuses, promotions, and pay raises, among other things. Performance appraisal system is not only an important tool for HRM to develop their employees, but it is also used by different companies to reward their employees in the form of bonuses, promotions, and pay raises, among other things. Different theories of motivation, such as reinforcement theory, use performance appraisal to reward personnel.

Sharma (2012)[8] 360-degree feedback entails anyone in the organisation who has interaction with an employee providing input on their performance. Self-appraisal, superior appraisal, subordinate appraisal, and peer appraisal are all included in the 360-degree appraisal. These methods are less organised than the traditional method, which places a greater emphasis on scheduling meetings between employees and supervisors and less on rankings and evaluations.

Usha Sri (2021)[9] Employee self-esteem is important because it opens the way to improved future performance appraisals. Most performance appraisals are subjective and rely on the opinions of managers and supervisors.

2.3 Employee's Performance

Gilliland and Langdon, (1998)[10] The performance rating system, incentives, motives, and innovations can have a negative impact and cause irritation if they are not fair.

Lawler (2003) [11] a company's human resources and its treatment of its employees are crucial to its success. It has been observed that companies succeed greatly if they follow their business strategy and provide a fair compensation and recognition system for their workers.

Sonntag and Frese (2002)[12] Performance is not only concerned with technical core features, but also with the psychological and social environments in which the organisation operates in order to achieve its goals. It entails actions such as assisting coworkers or being a dependable member of the company.

Boxall and Purcell (2003) [13] have opined that the objective of PA is not only to measure and manage employee performance but to integrate it to the organization's overall goals.

Varma, (2018)[14] Motivation leads to unified group/team direction, increased organisational commitment, increased efficiency and effectiveness, optimal resource use, and the development of a performance culture. Furthermore, according to this researcher, motivation fosters creativity and innovation, improves ability to deal with uncertainty and obstacles, increases employee retention, and attracts and retains experienced human capital.

2.4 Fairness of performance Appraisal Systems

Greenberg, (1986)[15] Procedural and distributive justice are the two approaches used in PA practise to determine whether the PA system is fair. Employees must be aware that the processes used to evaluate their performance are fair, whereas distributive justice means that the employee's input is proportional to his or her output.

Murphy & Cleveland, (1995)[16] Employees benefit from a formal appraisal system if it is regarded to be fair. Some conditions must be met for employees to accept the system as fair, including: employees must have technical knowledge of the job; there must be a platform for petitioning the feedback received; the instruments used for the exercise must be applicable; and a method for dealing with challenges as they arise must be devised. Instead of a circumstance where employees compete to prove who is better than the other, the environment where the PA is done should be accommodating.

Korsgaard & Roberson, (1995)[17] Supervisors should treat employees with respect and objectivity while reviewing their performance. If the procedure is to be effective, both the employee and the supervisor must have confidence in each other.

Colquitt, (2001)[18] Perceived fairness or organisational justice has been demonstrated to influence how employees behave in an organisation in terms of work fulfilment, resignation ideas, loyalty to the organisation, and organisational culture, such as failing to report to work, according to studies.

Cropanzano et al., (2007)[19] The practise of evaluating employee performance is an important part of ensuring organisational fairness. Individual perceptions of the organization's administration's honesty and fairness have been termed as organisational justice.

2.5 Performance Appraisal feedback

Taylor, Fisher, & Ilgen (1984)[20] Many firms fail to achieve PA results despite performing the exercise on a regular basis and storing the feedback in a secure location. Employees are worried about the outcome of the PA process, and when the organisation chooses not to communicate, the amount of time, effort, and cash invested is seen meaningless, and favourable work attitudes may not develop.

Baumeister, (1999)[21] Feedback on how an employee is doing in respect to their assignment is usually beneficial and helps an employee perform better. They should receive a response that is specific, reasonable, and measurable, as agreed upon previously. Every employee is entitled to a status report on the actions taking place in their area of responsibility. People are always judging themselves, and in many cases, they wish to compare their self-judgments to

those of others.

Gabris and Ihrke (2000)[22] The primary goal of performance appraisal is to provide regular and formal feedback to individual employees

Smither, London, & Reilly (2005)[23] PAs are used for both administrative and developmental purposes, like as promotions, wage increases, and termination. Employee feedback may be the most essential information about the PA system that employees receive in a business, as it relates to genuine ratings that reflect appreciation, value, and future prospects. Employees who receive and accept performance feedback are often assumed to be more positive and objective, which improves organisational performance and leads to increased productivity. Conversely, when evaluations do not meet the employees' expectations and they reject them, they develop negative energy about potential rewards.

Nawaz, Jahanian, & Manzoor (2012)[24] Performance feedback is a critical component of the PA process in businesses, and no organisation can improve productivity if employees are unaware of how they are performing in respect to the organization's goals. As a result, the primary goal of performance feedback should be to improve performance by motivating employees to produce more quantity and quality output. As a result, it is critical to convey employee performance development in a way that leads to total employee growth.

Swan (2012)[25] One of the most popular justifications for an organisation to use a performance appraisal system is to provide feedback. Employees understand exactly what they performed throughout the work time through the process of performance appraisal, and they utilise that information as a reference point to better their future performance, he continues. In this sense, performance appraisal feedback ensures that the employer's requirements are stated clearly.

2.6 Uses of Performance Appraisal Results

Drucker (1990)[26] The use of PA as a planning tool for businesses. Human resource planning and replacements have continued to be done using PA. In the workplace, PA has also been utilised to protect employers from discrimination lawsuits.

Mullins (2002)[27] The primary goal of PA is to improve employee performance, which leads to increased profitability for the company.

Brown & Heywood (2005)[28] Performance appraisal is a method of systematically assessing employee performance and identifying strategies to improve workers' performance and productivity.

Mathis and Jackson (2008)[29] PA's uses are divided into two categories: managerial and

developmental. PA is utilised in the managerial function to determine staff pay and promotions, among other things. While in developmental mode, the emphasis is on increasing and improving staff capabilities as well as advancing their career paths.

Ojokuku (2013)[30] PA is a tool that may be applied to properly administer performance since it provides data that feeds into other aspects of the performance management process. PA, when used for its intended purpose, can help with motivation, job performance, and efficiency.

Mathew and Johnson (2015)[31] stated that performance appraisal system used to improve the employee performance that will leads towards the organization success. The results indicate that there is a set of performance appraisal practices which are widely used in the industry.

Rohan Singh and Madhumita & Mohanty.A.K (2010) [32] stated that performance appraisal has become an essential requirement of every organization to properly evaluate the performance of its employees.

Riggio (2017)[33] Individual employee and unit performance is measured by PA. It also acts as a means of endorsing recruitment procedures, methods of identifying and motivating personnel, and methods of determining the efficiency of intervention strategies such as training.

2.7 Motivation

Hackman & Oldham (1976)[34] Motivation is the inner impulse that drives a person to pursue a specific goal.

Golshan & Abraham (1996)[35] Motivation, as a requirement for work, is a critical component in improving employee performance. Employee learning, aptitudes, inventiveness, organisational climate, and management style are all important aspects in employee performance.

Grote (2002)[36] the manager tries to meet the demands of the employees, and performance appraisal is the most effective way among the alternatives.

Basset-Jones and Lloyd (2009)[37] Employee motivation is the process of stimulating and driving people to achieve their objectives. Performance assessments that are well-designed and executed have a significant motivating effect on employees' performance. Employees are motivated by appraisals because they deliver a range of interconnected rewards.

Shaukat & Surraya (2013)[38] According to the literature, in order to achieve market share in the fastest expanding markets, it is vital to employ innovative human resource practises and motivation.

2.8 Performance Appraisal and Employee Motivation

Krietner (1995)[39] In organisations, motivation gave an indication that operations and activities are on track. The efforts of a person lead to the maximisation of profits, which offers the company a competitive advantage in the market. Employees that are inspired and excited are more focused and satisfied with their accomplishments, and thus will devote the majority of their time to improving what makes them happy, lowering labour turnover.

Byars & Rue (2000)[40] Many firms' compensation systems are based on managers' performance appraisals. PA is the process of establishing standards, evaluating employee performance against those standards, providing feedback to employees on their performance, and making strategies for improvement.

Hodgetts & Chamberlain (2002)[41] The performance appraisal system is divided into four steps. Establishing performance criteria, determining individual performance, comparing performance to standards, and evaluating performance based on the comparison are all part of a performance appraisal system.

Rue and Byars (2005)[42] Performance appraisal is a method of determining and conveying how people execute their duties, as well as developing a strategy for improving the process of carrying out works obligations.

Kuvaas (2006)[43] As a means of improving people, PA also comprises capacity building through training by adding new information and abilities. When a firm builds the capability of its employees, there is always a desire to repay the organisation by improving and increasing performance.

Selvarajan & Cloninger (2008)[44] The performance appraisal procedure in some firms is dissatisfactory. This means that performance appraisals are ineffective at motivating employees. However, performance evaluations are thought to be necessary for fostering a healthy work atmosphere and improving service quality.

Vasset, Marnburg and Furunes (2011)[45] The performance appraisal system is a major initiative that aims to find better, more accurate, and more cost-effective ways to assess work performance and employee motivation. A performance appraisal system is an important tool for improving an employee's performance in the workplace.

Selvarajan and Cloninger (2012)[46] Employee motivation is commonly acknowledged as a vital component of a performance appraisal system. The performance appraisal process has a number of flaws, including bad design, a lack of attention to corporate culture, and a refusal to tackle issues of poor performance, as well as time constraints. The following section examines the various performance evaluation processes and their impact on employee

motivation, focusing on both past and future ways.

Aggarwal and Thakur (2013)[47] a formal system for retaining employees accountable by providing accurate assessment and evaluation of several aspects of their performance.

Kamiti (2014)[48] the impact of performance appraisal on public servant motivation demonstrated that performance evaluation is a critical aspect that affects employee motivation. Apart from monetary incentives, the study advised that promotions and trainings inspire civil servants. To summarise, the majority of these empirical research have found that there is a link between performance appraisal and employee motivation.

The combined findings of the many pieces of literature suggested that performance evaluation is a challenging task encompassing a variety of complex organisational, process, and human level issues. Due to the difficulties of the procedure, studies that looked at discrete elements in controlled settings were more common in the past. Recent studies have examined the phenomenon of organisational context and attitudinal influence on raters, ratees, and performance assessment findings by using more field studies, surveys, and self-report measures, as well as some analysis of real performance appraisal paperwork. Employee satisfaction must be the main factor in any performance appraisal system review. Employee happiness is closely related to how they feel about how fair the organisational system is. The notions of organisational justice can be used to examine how fairness is perceived in performance reviews. The performance appraisal systems of various service sector firms in Kerala will be evaluated for their efficacy using the satisfaction and perceived fairness of an existing performance appraisal system, which will be organised according to the organisational justice theory.

Different companies use different approaches or procedures for their performance appraisal practises. As a result, the nature and operationalization of the notion of performance appraisal change as well. PA is also act as a motivational tool. This study used to find out the effect of performance appraisal on employee motivation in media and entertainment sector in Kerala.

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CHAPTER 3

THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Motivation plays a significant role in forecasting the success of individuals and their capability to perform in the workplace. The precise mechanism by which motivation is influenced has been studied by psychologists. In an effort to better understand how motivation affects human performance, numerous theorists (including Maslow, Herzberg, McGregor, and McClelland) have made substantial contributions to study on human behaviour. Managers that want to increase employee enthusiasm, performance, and productivity have tested the findings in the real world. The use of more modern theories of motivation has come to light in the commercial world of today. Understanding motivation in today's complicated work environment requires consideration of theories like John Stacy Adams' Equity theory and Victor Vroom's Expectancy theory.

The combined efforts of the key motivation theory scholars are valid in and of it. It is not unexpected that companies aiming to boost motivation as a means of boosting productivity are actively studying and putting their theories to use. At the absolute least, managers can expand on the framework provided by the motivation study (to motivate staff). Examining some of the more recent theories, like the equity and expectancy theories put forth by Adams and Vroom, may help us better grasp the effect that motivation has on today's businesses. This study is anchored on the equity theory and expectancy theory of motivation.

3.1 Equity Theory

Adams first proposed the Equality Theory of Motivation in 1965, and it aims to explain how a person's impression of equity can influence their actions. Adams (1965)[1] discussed two types of equity: distributive equity, which is the employee's perception of fairness in terms of the ratio of efforts to remuneration received and in comparison to others; and procedural equity, which is the employee's perception of how procedures such as performance appraisal, advancement, and punishment are implemented.

Carrell & Dittrich (1978)[2] Equity theory is based on three assumptions. One of them is that various people/employees have varied views on what amounts to a just or equitable compensation for their contribution to or effort on the job. The second observation is that individuals and/or employees regularly contrast what they have received in exchange from the

employer. The final point is that if people believe they are being treated unfairly in comparison to others, they will be compelled to take action. Equity theory is linked to an employee's success and the rewards they receive in terms of pay and other benefits.

Pinder (1984) [3] Established that perceptions of inequity in the workplace arise when employees believe they are not receiving an equitable/commensurate reward for their efforts/performance and other contributions at work.

Champagne & McAfee (1989) [4] Employees may reduce their contribution to the organisation, increase their contribution/performance to leverage for a greater return, or look for pleasurable assignments that can provide equivalent return for performance/contribution in other organisations when they generate such a sense among themselves.

Robbins (1993) [5] Individuals are bothered not just by what they obtain as a whole compensation package for their efforts, but also by what other people receive in comparison to theirs, according to the Equity theory. People tend to aggregate their input in terms of abilities, experience, and education, and then compare it to their output in terms of money, recognition, and other characteristics. There is tension when people believe what they are putting in is not comparable with what they are receiving in return. This friction functions as a catalyst for what is ostensibly fairness.

Selvarajan and Cloninger (2012) [6] They looked at the association between performance appraisal characteristics (appraisal source, purpose, and feedback richness) and employees' perceptions of appraisal characteristics (perceived fairness and accuracy of appraisals) and appraisal outcomes (appraisal satisfaction and motivation to improve). The findings of the study revealed that fair performance appraisals had a favourable impact on employee motivation and job satisfaction.

Fairness reinforces motivation; people like to compare themselves to those in the organisation who are in the same or similar categories as them. Employees who believe they are treated unfairly in comparison to others are likely to get demotivated, and vice versa. According to equity theory, if an employee feels fairly treated, he or she will be driven to do better in their job since what they put in and the return they receive are seen as equal. It's unclear how employees feel about the PA process and whether or not it's a fair one. This research will close the gap by determining how fair PAS is seen by employees.

3.2 Equity Theory of Motivation

John Stacey Adams, a workplace behavioural psychologist, created Adam's Equity Theory, commonly referred to as the Equity Theory of Motivation, in 1963. The foundation of equity

theory is the notion that people are driven by justice. Simply put, according to equity theory, if a person notices unfairness between themselves and a peer, they will change what they do to make the situation right in their eyes. As an illustration of equity theory, if a worker discovers that a colleague receiving the exact same amount of money as them, they can decide to work less to make things seem more equitable in their view.

From this, Adam's Equity Theory extrapolates that a person will be more driven if they see equity (fairness) as being higher. If they sense unfairness, on the other hand, a person will become demotivated.

3.3 Functionality of Equity Theory of Motivation

The equity theory of motivation directly relates a person's motivation to their perception of fairness, known as "equity." This means that your motivation is highly correlated to fairness and justice, both in the workplace as well as in the outside world. The higher the fairness and justice, the more motivated a person typically becomes.

People motivated by equity typically evaluate their level of fairness by comparing specific inputs like effort and enthusiasm to desired outcomes like compensation or self-worth. If the chosen inputs result in the expected or desired outcomes, things are perceived to be fair and a person is more motivated. Alternatively, if the inputs don't result in the expected outcome, it's possible to become demotivated.

Additionally, people frequently contrast their perspective of equity with their impression of the equity of others. As a result, people frequently compare themselves to others and may lose motivation if they feel that they are both under and overpaid in comparison to others. To feel motivated, people need to believe that they are treated fairly in relation to others and themselves.

A person almost always judges fairness using one of four "referents" or references. The type of reference you use to gauge your performance is crucial to motivation. If you can identify the referent that you or another person is employing, you can work to boost motivation and justice.

The following are among the four categories of referents:

- Self-inside: Analyse present circumstances in light of previous circumstances within the same group or organisation.
- Self-outside: Compare present circumstances with earlier ones outside of the company or group.

- Other-inside: Compare one's own experiences with those of someone else who is a member of the same organisation or group.
- Other-outside: Compare your experiences with those of someone outside your organisation or group.

The key to understanding how someone views fairness is to comprehend these reference experiences. With the use of this motivational theory, you can concentrate on the proper inputs and outputs that boost motivation once you've determined which of the four referents you or another person uses to assess fairness.

3.4 Common Inputs & Outputs affects Equity

An "input" is something a person performs to get a certain result. The traditional definition of inputs is a person's contribution to himself, other people, or a bigger organisation. People anticipate receiving the desired output or outcome in exchange for these inputs. For instance, someone may exert effort and anticipate a reward such as a raise in pay.

A person is motivated if the chosen inputs produce the intended outcome and the experience is satisfying. It might get discouraging if the chosen input does not provide the desired consequence. This is why it's crucial to comprehend the inputs you or another person are concentrating on and the anticipated outcomes.

3.5 Inputs that Affect Equity & Motivation

The following are typical inputs that lead to fairness and motivation:

- Effort: The time you devote to a person, project, or organisation
- Commitment: The degree of involvement you have with individuals, endeavours, or organisations
- Enthusiasm: The enthusiasm you or others exhibit for persons, things, or organisations
- Experience: How much expertise you bring to a task or position
- Selflessness through putting others' needs before of your own: Personal sacrifice
- Loyalty: The exhibited degree of allegiance one displays toward other individuals or groups
- Flexibility: The capacity to take things in stride and change one's behaviour in response to novel circumstances

3.6 Outputs that Affect Equity & Motivation

Common outputs that result in fairness and motivation include:

- Monetary compensation: Salary, bonus, pension, stock options, increased revenue, and more
- Increase in free time: The ability to spend your time as you see fit, such as creating a lifestyle business or getting extra vacation days at work
- Recognition and accomplishment: The feeling of self-worth and that your work is meaningful
- Learning: The chance to learn new skills and gain greater life experiences

A person will feel unfairly treated and their motivation will decrease if the inputs they invest don't provide the outcomes they anticipate. You'll be able to encourage yourself as well as the people around you if you can pinpoint what you or another person is investing in and what you or they anticipate earning in return.

3.7 The Optimal Ratio of Equity for Motivation

Although it might seem logical to assume that greater justice or a sense of fairness leads to greater motivation, this isn't exactly the case. One always wants to be treated fairly and build up their own equity, but they also want to make sure they aren't getting paid unfairly in comparison to those around them.

The four referents we previously mentioned come into play here. A person will feel that things are unfair and lose motivation if they think that they have either more or less equity than their selected reference. The term for this is "equity tension." You lose motivation if you believe that you are being underpaid and have less equity than your reference.

To ensure that no one feels overly or underappreciated, it is crucial to treat others the same way you want to be treated. Make careful to use the following ratio to help prevent creating equity tension:

- Under-rewarded (equity tension): When a person's input or output is less equitable than that of their reference.
- The optimum equity ratio: It occurs when a person's input and output are equally fair when compared to those of their reference.
- Over-rewarded (equity tension): When a person's input or output is more equitable than that of their reference.

- Therefore, it's crucial that you try to establish equal justice throughout the board when you're trying to push yourself or others. People will be motivated by this because they will realise that their efforts will be rewarded.

3.8 The Equity Theory of Motivation in Business

The equity theory of motivation is a common management tool in business. You are more concerned with the motivation of others in your organization—specifically, those with whom you collaborate and for whom you are responsible—than you are with your own. In this situation, it's critical to recognise the inputs, intended outcomes, and references of your subordinates before they lose motivation so that you can hasten their advancement within your organisation.

To motivate people in the organization, we must take the following 3 steps:

1. Define outputs for individuals: This may seem backward, but it's crucial to first comprehend what the individuals in your organisation desire. What are their objectives and expectations during their time working for you? By rewarding them with the things they genuinely want, like growth or independence, you will be able to drive them.

2. Recognize people's contributions: Once you've figured out what people want, explain them how to get there and congratulate them when they make the appropriate choice. For instance, if someone in your business has to exert more effort to complete a task, identify those instances when they do so and give them praise.

3. Understanding how they compare themselves is crucial because, unlike you, who might evaluate yourself in light of past experiences, others might do so in light of their peers today. You can never drive individuals in your organisation if you don't know how they view justice and unfairness.

3.9 The Equity Theory of Motivation for Personal Use

Numerous personal applications of the equity theory of motivation are possible. Refer to the aforementioned technique by attempting to identify your outputs, inputs, and referents first if you're feeling demotivated because you don't have a clear aim in mind.

The current labour of love (and other inputs) aren't producing the outcomes you want if you have a goal but are unable to realise it. You have a choice between three options when this occurs. Altering your inputs, your desired results, or the benchmark against which you measure your fairness to others are all options.

The three actions you should do if you notice that your motivation is waning are as follows:

1. Change your inputs: If your current course of action isn't leading to the life you desire, alter it! Consider how your present strategy is expected to help you reach your objectives. How can your path be changed so that your desired outcomes are maintained even as your inputs change?

2. Change your outputs: If, after altering your inputs, you still aren't accomplishing your goals and you're losing motivation, it's time to modify your goals. Perhaps you no longer want what you once believed you did. Perhaps your objectives are unrealistic for your available means. Even a minor change in your outputs can make you feel more motivated.

3. Change your references: If you're still lacking motivation, it's possible that you're comparing yourself to the wrong examples. For instance, compare your present self to your prior self rather than comparing yourself to others. You might be able to regain some of your lost motivation with the use of this.

3.10 Assumptions of the Equity Theory of Motivation

Key presumptions must be made in the equity theory of motivation. The equity theory can help you become more motivated if the presumptions are correct. If not, it is a failure and ought to be replaced with a different idea or strategy.

The following are the main presumptions of the equity theory of motivation:

- Inputs and outputs are highly associated
- Individuals are capable of achieving their intended results.
- People frequently receive rewards for their good work.
- Fair and just reward systems exist for all individuals and organisations.
- Individuals regularly evaluate their motivation and make appropriate course corrections.

3.11 Expectancy theory

Victor Vroom created the Expectancy Theory in 1964. According to the Expectancy Theory, a person is driven to act in a particular way by a combination of three perceptions: valence, which refers to the value the employee or person places on the anticipated end result, instrumentality, which is the belief that better performance will lead to esteemed results, and expectancy, which is the belief that more effort will result in better performance. According to the Expectancy Theory, a person's decision to behave in a given way is based on the expected outcome and the value a person assigns to it. Robbins, (1993) [7] .

Salaman, Storey & Billsberry (2005) [8] It goes on to say that an individual's activities will

change in order to achieve fulfillment by accomplishing the aims and future goals they set.

The expectation that the results of the PA process will lead to a desired outcome, such as a reward if an employee meets their goals, which could be in the form of a promotion, recognition, or a raise in income. Employees will be more motivated as a result of this.

Fudge & Schlacter (1999) [9] Expectancy theory, is a process theory of motivation that emphasises personal opinions of the work setting as a result of expectancies. Employees achieve and surpass goals in an environment that is stimulating to them, resulting in enhanced performance in the organisation.

PA is the only instrument that can help determine whether there has been an improvement or goal achievement when the right procedure is followed, where employees and supervisors set the targets at the beginning of a specified period in an environment that allows them to monitor and achieve the results. When this occurs, there is an expectation of being rewarded or penalised.

Performance management has been recognised as a system that establishes the context for ongoing monitoring and measurement of employee activities within a company. In a similar vein, it assesses the effectiveness of the entire organisation to ensure that organisational goals are achieved (Lebas 1995) [8]. An important theory that supports the idea of performance management is expectancy theory (Fletcher & Williams 1996; Steers et al. 2004) [9] [10]

3.12 Elements of expectancy theory

Victor Vroom put forth the expectancy theory of performance management in 1965. He argues that people act in a certain way because they are driven by the positive results of doing so. Individual performance should always be in line with organisational objectives for reaching defined future goals (Salaman et al. 2005) [11]. Individuals' expectations serve as the driving force behind their preference for one type of behaviour over another. This expectation relates to how the chosen behaviour will have an impact (Oliver 1974 ; Salaman et al. 2005) [12][13].

Expectancy is based on an individual's conviction that engaging in a particular behaviour will unquestionably assist them in achieving their intended performance goals. As a result, this attribute aids people in identifying whether or not they possess the necessary skill sets for successfully completing a task. However, the accompanying drive also decreases when performance goals are above what can be accomplished.

Instrumentality is linked to the practise of rewarding desirable performance results. Individuals are thereby inspired to carry out tasks that, upon successful completion, will yield

higher rewards. But when the instrumentality or compensation for a variety of organisational achievements is the same, motivation to carry out various sorts of labour falls.

Valence is the importance of the reward people receive for exhibiting desired behaviours. As a result, people assess the incentives they receive for their performance based on a number of factors. This covers varying requirements, values, ambitions, and motivational factors. The drives to complete various tasks also alter depending on valence (Burgoon 1993; Kroth 2007) [14][15]. Individuals therefore prioritise the factor that has the most motivating force when selecting how to behave.

Figure 3.1: Expectancy Theory Model

3.13 Application of expectancy theory

Practical applications of expectancy theory can be found in almost all sorts of organisations. This is mostly used to monitor employee performance in all facets of the work relationship (Eisenberger et al. 1990) [16]. Expectancy theory is applied in organisational procedures like hiring and choosing individuals for a given position. Similar to that, it is also used to analyse the results of organisational training and evaluate employee performance in accordance with organisational goals (Hillman & Dalziel 2003; Noe 1986; Rynes et al. 1980) [17] [18] [19].

On the other hand, this idea is also used to pinpoint the elements that drive each employee's motivation within the organisation. This theory specifically aids in identifying the factors that

encourage people to join an organisation based on needs, aspirations, and prior experiences when it comes to employee recruitment and selection.

This theory attempts to analyse the distinctive behaviour that employees display based on their own expectancy calculations in the assessment of organisational performance. It should be noted that the expectancy theory also holds that various people have varied expectations of their organisations. This includes a competitive wage, work security, and opportunities for career advancement.

As a result, this theory aids in mapping the behavioural outcomes of organisational training. In other words, this approach aids in determining the precise factors that underlie a specific trainee's behavioural outcome (Lunenburg 2011) [20].

3.14 Advantages of expectancy theory and the corresponding organisational impact

In many aspects, expectancy theory is superior to other theories. For instance, it aids in recognising self-interested employees who are eager to give their all in a workplace. If the proper motivator is offered to these individuals, they can experience the highest level of job satisfaction. As a result, the idea aids in understanding personal psychologies. This in turn aids in identifying the unique motivators that lead individuals to make decisions based on their unique expectations (Kanfer 1990; Ramlall 2004) [21] [22].

Additionally, the focus of this idea is on how employees should behave in the workplace and how the organisation should be seen. As a result, it aids in raising awareness among employees regarding organisational behaviour and ensuing organisational expectations. On the other hand, organisations might use this idea to determine the actual performance of their personnel. Therefore, by recognising their distinct intrinsic and extrinsic motivators, this theory aids them in keeping employees who can provide value to their company (Ramlall 2004 ; Samuel, Osinowo & Chipunza 2009) [23] [24].

3.15 Limitation of expectancy theory

The expectation theory is frequently criticised for having too high of ideals. The attributes for performance measurement in expectancy theory is motivation, employee effort, value of rewards, etc. These characteristics are challenging to measure, though. In order to measure and track individual performances, managers frequently need to combine expectation theory with other performance measurement theories (Parijat & Bagga 2014) [25].

Additionally, the model assumes that people will calculate these variables in a reasonable and rational manner. However, in practise, the theory falls short of offering precise solutions to

particular motivational issues. Second, the theory is complex due to the participation of numerous factors. Due to this, it is challenging to both assess the employee incentive variables and use them in a variety of contexts (Parijat & Bagga 2014) [26].

In organisations with adequate infrastructure, expectation theory is preferable to other theories like goal-setting theory, claim Robbins and Judge (2013) [27]. The appropriate system for gauging employee efforts, results, and rewards is referred to in this context as the infrastructure. However, in other organisations without such an infrastructure, this idea might not work as well.

3.16 Equity verses Expectancy

According to the expectation theory, people try to maximise their favourable outcomes. As opposed to this, the equity hypothesis proposes that people attempt to strike a balance between their inputs and outcomes (Vecchio, 1981) [28]. According to equity theory, people care about their rewards in terms of both their total value and how it compares to the rewards of others. According to the notion, workers compare things. Employee effort might be influenced by disparities when they compare their own job inputs and outcomes to those of others. Employees could, for instance, compare their input-output ratio to the ratios of others by weighing what they put into a job scenario (input) against what they get out of it (outcome). If people see equity, they believe that justice has been done and that their condition is fair. If the ratios are unbalanced, there is injustice, and they will feel either under- or over-compensated. Equity theory takes into account the equity or inequity within a group while Expectancy theory emphasises self interest in the alignment of rewards with employees' desires.

According to the expectation theory, the likelihood that an action will result in a particular outcome and how desirable that consequence is to the individual determine how strong a tendency to take that action will be (Vroom, 1964) [29]. There are three factors: attractiveness (how much value the person attaches to the potential outcome or reward that can be obtained on the job); performance-reward linkage (to what extent the person believes that performing at a particular level will result in the attainment of a desired outcome); and effort-performance linkage (the perceived probability that exerting a given amount of effort will lead to performance). Between the Expectancy theory and the Equity theory, Harder (1991) [30] highlighted a key distinction. According to the equity theory, a person would be driven to lower the imbalance by lowering his performance if he felt that he was being

underpaid. On the other side, the Expectancy theory contends that if a person strongly believes that the outcome will be favourable, they may perform better.

Managers can utilise motivational theories as helpful tools to create a rewards system and figure out what drives their people. Every theory of motivation has important ramifications for managers working in the current global setting. While attempting to adjust to the new cultural requirements that come with globalisation, managers must balance employee job satisfaction, motivation, and performance. Additionally, managers must create a culture that supports productivity and high morale in their changing enterprises. Finding out what motivates their staff and putting in place a flexible compensation plan to suit everyone is a significant element of this issue.

Adams (1965) [31] asserts that managers need to take into account the fact that workers will create situational comparisons between themselves and their coworkers. If an employee discovers an injustice through this comparison, it may have a major negative effect on their motivation. Therefore, it is crucial that managers comprehend that they must treat all employees fairly even when they may not do so uniformly. As they give out awards based on standards, managers must maintain an environment of equity and justice by adhering to a set code of conduct. Additionally, by setting a baseline for incentives and rewards, workers will know what to anticipate from their employers. They will comprehend that they will earn a predetermined reward by upholding certain work ethics and accomplishing particular objectives.

As previously said, Expectancy theory demonstrates a strong relationship between rewards and the quantity of work required to get the reward. If standards are defined and expectations are provided regularly, managers will be better able to forecast performance and employees will be aware of their place at any given time within the business. In a similar vein, managers must be familiar with motivational ideas. They will be more equipped to address motivation by using their expertise in the workplace if they have a firm grasp of theory. They will undoubtedly become more adept at identifying motivational problems and better equipped to effect change, even though there is no assurance that they will be successful in putting theory into practise.

3.17 Conceptual Framework

The independent variable of the study is performance evaluation, which is operationalized as setting work-related goals, involving employees in the process fairly, providing timely feedback, and using data. The dependent variable is employee motivation, which is

demonstrated by initiative, teamwork, problem-solving, high-quality work, and passionate workers.

PA is chosen by the employer as a performance evaluation measure. The method in which the assessment instrument is used has the potential to either disappoint or stimulate personnel to achieve the organization's goals. The PA process' result informs the employer about the worth of the personnel in the company.

Figure 3.2: PA and Employee Motivation Model

3.18 Research Hypothesis

The study was guided by the following hypotheses:

- H1: There is a significant impact of performance appraisal on employee motivation
- H2. There is a significant impact of fairness of performance appraisal system
- H3. There is a significant impact of feedback on performance appraisal
- H4. There is a significant impact of use of performance appraisal results

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CHAPTER 4

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Introduction

Data analysis and interpretation is the process in which meaning is assigned to the information gathered and meaningful insights are found. Data integrity is needed for accurate and suitable analysis in accordance with Resnik & Shampoo (2009). Improper statistical analysis leads to mislead results (Shepard, 2002) and directly influences research perception of researchers. This chapter consists of seven sections. Throughout the work, the first part deals with data exploration, in the second part the preliminary data analysis is presented, third part deals with exploratory factor analysis, fourth part present research model, the fifth part discuss confirmative factor analyses, sixth part deals with reliability analysis, seventh-part deals with validity analysis and eight-part, structural equation modelling is presented.

The first phase of data analysis includes data exploration that usually comprises the features of a dataset. During the data exploration, the researcher knows about the number of cases and variables inside the data set. This even helps to identify the lack of observations with designs since they have a powerful impact on the parameters of the model being tested.

The preliminary data analysis was done with the help of SPSS 23.0 and “Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM).” Results are presented in terms of reliability, validity of tool and the descriptive analysis in the context of demographic findings. The fifth, sixth, seventh and eight part of this chapter consists of the analysis done with the help of PLS-SEM. PLS-SEM was used to apply Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). CFA was used to verify the factor structure of a set of observed variables.

SEM was used to examine the relationship between the independent and dependent factors considered in the conceptual model.

4.2 Data Exploration

It is a first initial step in data analysis. In a data exploration the researcher explores the data set to uncover patterns, and data characteristics. By doing this the researcher gets the broad picture regarding the initial trends and major points which to be studied in detail. However, this process does not mean to explore every information holds by dataset. Data exploration can be conducted by using automated and manual tools namely charts, data visualization and initial reports. Data exploration makes deeper analysis easier by beginning the process of excluding irrelevant data and makes the data refine. Traditionally, data analyst used the manual methods involving filtering and deep search into spreadsheet but with the help automated methods, it makes the process quickly. Thus, successfully exploring the dataset will ensure refine data.

4.2.1. Missing Values and Outliers

When no data is stored for a particular variable then it shows the missing data and missing values. Typically, it is a common occurrence and may lead to false information drawn from data. It occurs when people do not respond for a particular variable. The researcher sometimes leads to missing values, and this may happen due to improper data collection or mistakes made during the data entry, editing and coding process. Missing data leads to inability to interpret the accurate results and total score of the variable. “Generally, there are three kinds of missing data namely Missing completely at random (MCAR), missing at random (MAR), and missing not at random (MNAR).” In MCAR, missingness is nothing to do with the person being studied it means data are missing and it is independent of observed and unobserved data (Alvo, 2002).

When data are MCAR, the data analysis performed introduced biasness; however, data are rarely MCAR. Data considered to be missing at random (MAR), when missingness is conditionally at random. Here missing data have an association with another variable in a dataset (Ray, 2016). Missing not at random (MNAR) can be seen as a specific pattern of missingness and have an association with other variables in the dataset (Ray, 2016). Thus, for carrying out proper data analysis, it is very much important to handle missing values. Missing data leads to false inferences drawn from the population. Previous studies have suggested many ways to treat missing values. One way is deletion, and the other is imputation. In this study, list wise deletion technique was used to delete cases with missing values completely at random. The power of model is reduced because it reduced the sample size. Data imputation was performed to replace missing values that were not randomly distributed across the observations. “Imputation simply means to replace missing values with guessed and

estimated ones. A simple guess of a missing values is the mean/ mode/median of that variable.”

Missing values were replaced by median for the statements based upon the five-point Likert scale (Lynch, 2009). The rest of the missing values were replaced by mean According to Ray (2016) “*Outlier is an observation that appears far away and diverges from an overall pattern in a sample*”. An outlier could be univariate and multivariate. In a univariate case, it is an extreme value that falls outside the data values for a single variable. In a multivariate case, it is combination of unusual scores on a at least two variables. Before proceeding to data analysis, it necessary to detect and remove outliers because it impacts the parameter being tested. According to Zimmerman (1994) “the presence of outliers can lead to inflated error rates and substantial distortions of parameter and statistic estimates when using either parametric or nonparametric tests”. Coleby and duffy (2005) suggest that “*outliers should be reduced with the help of box plots*”. A box and whisker plot displays five number summaries of a set of data in terms of minimum, first quarterly, median, third quarterly and maximum. Brochardo, (2009) stated “Inter quartile range (IQR) shows where the bulk of the data lies and the dispersion of the data”. After the treatment of missing values, “outliers were detected with the help of box plots in SPSS 23.0.”

4.2.2. Normally Distributed Data

Normality refers to how the values of a variable are distributed. In fact, it is a most important probability distribution in statistics. “In this study, the normality of the data is assessed by skewness, kurtosis, and Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) tests.” Skewness refers to asymmetry that deviates from normal distribution curve. If the curve is shifted to left or right it is said to be skewed. Distribution can exhibit right (positive) skewness or left (negative) skewness and a normal distribution exhibit zero skewness. According to Malhotra (2006) “*Kurtosis is a measure that defines how heavily the tails of a distribution differ from the tails of a normal distribution*”. For a data to be normally distributed, both skewness and kurtosis must be zero (Field, 2006). According to Cameron (2012) skewness and kurtosis should fall within the range of -2 to +2. When the K-S value goes below 0.05, the data is not normally distributed (Field, 2006). In this study, K-S values are above 0.05. This indicates that data is normally distributed. Table 4.1 shows the statistics of Normality Test of the data used in the present study.

Table 4.1: Statistics of Normality Test of the Data

Items	Skewness		Kurtosis		K-S ^a	
	Stats	SE	Stats	Sig	Stats	SE
SWRG	-0.862	0.106	0.668	0.213	0.118	0.239
EP	-0.919	0.106	0.968	0.213	0.158	0.239
FIP	-0.891	0.106	0.89	0.213	0.141	0.239
UOR	-0.797	0.106	0.812	0.213	0.134	0.239
TF	-0.816	0.106	1.042	0.213	0.145	0.239
INT	-0.516	0.106	0.239	0.213	0.13	0.239
PS	-0.589	0.106	0.252	0.213	0.134	0.239
TW	-0.79	0.106	0.683	0.213	0.15	0.239
EM	-0.53	0.106	0.2	0.213	0.139	0.239
QOW	-0.363	0.106	0.29	0.213	0.138	0.239

Key: **SWRG**-Setting work related goals, **EP** -Employee participation, **FIP**-Fairness in the process, **UOR**-Usage of results, **TF**- Timely feedback, **INT**- Initiative, **PS**- Problem solving, **TW**-Team work, **EM**- Enthusiastic employees, **QOW**- Quality of work

Note: Criteria for the normality of data

- a. Skewness: +2 to -2 (Pallant, 2001; Cameron, 2012)
- b. Kurtosis: +2 to -2 (Sposito, 1983; Cameron, 2012)
- c. K-S Test: Not significant (viz. sig. value should be > 0.05) (Field, 2006)

From the Table 4.1, skewness and kurtosis of 10 items are within the range as specified in above table. Further, Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for normality also shows that data is normally distributed.

4.2.4. Independent Responses

It is assumed that the data from different respondents in the survey are independent of each other (Field, 2006). This implies that the behaviour of one participant does not influence that of another (Malhotra, 2003). Due care was taken to ensure that the respondents involved during the final survey of the questionnaire didn't get any chances of mutual interaction with each other. It can be inferred from the above discussions that the data collected for this

research study confirms to all the assumptions required for parametric tests. So, parametric testing was considered as a viable option for the present study.

4.3 Preliminary Data Analysis

4.3.1 Demographics

Descriptive and inferential statistics have been employed for such purposes of the present study. Tables, chart and quantitative methods was used to synthesise data are descriptive statistics “(for instance calculations of numerical summaries such as frequencies, averages, percentages, standard deviations etc.)” The qualities of the sample as well as the fundamental properties of the data in research can be described. Descriptive statistics are the cornerstone of almost all quantitative data analysis together along with simple graph analysis (Trochim, 2002). Inferential statistics are used to examine issues, models and hypotheses. Only the immediate data is very often found to be inferred using inferential statistics (Babbie and Mouton,2010). Therefore, inferential statistics are also used to deduce more general terms from of the data whereas descriptive statistics have been used to explain what happens in data. Data from of the frequency and percentage of respondents in just this survey are indicated when they could choose just a response choice from the list of options supplied inside the questionnaire. The number of responses collected when respondents were asked to respond from the item inside the questionnaire should be considered. Table 4.2 shows the demographic profile.

On the basis of gender distribution, 55.2% are male and 44.8% are female. According to age, 34% belongs to age group of 18-35 years, 23.2% belongs to age group of 36-45 years, 23.6% belongs to age group of 46-55 years, and 19.2% belongs to age group of above 55 years.

Table 4.2: Summary of the Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	138	55.2
	Female	112	44.8
Age	18-35 years	85	34
	36-45 years	58	23.2
	46-55 years	59	23.6
	Above 55 years	48	19.2
Highest level of education	Graduation	116	46.4
	Post-graduation	92	36.8

	Professional Degree	42	16.8
Job position	Senior management	26	10.4
	Middle management	137	54.8
	Operations staff	87	34.8
Working in organisation	Below one year	27	10.8
	1-3 years	59	23.6
	4-6 years	66	26.4
	7-9 years	54	21.6
	10 years and above	44	17.6

On the basis of educational qualification, 46.4% respondents are graduated, 36.8% respondents are post graduated and 16.8% respondents have professional degree. On the basis of job position, 10.4% respondents are senior manager, 54.8% respondents are middle manager and 34.8% respondents are operational staff. On the basis of working in organisation, 23.6% respondents are working below year, 26.4% respondents are working from 4-6 years, 21.6% respondents are working from 7-9 years, and 17.6% respondents are working from 10 years and above.

4.3.2 Statistics related to performance appraisal in general

In this section, statistics related to performance appraisal has been discussed.

Table 4.3: Summary of the statistics related to performance appraisal policy

Statement	Yes	No
Does your organization have a performance appraisal policy?	138 (55.2)	112 (44.8)

From above table it is observed that, 55.2% respondents agreed that organization have a performance appraisal policy and 44.8% respondents denied with the statement.

Table 4.4: Summary of the statistics related to effective and efficient administration of performance appraisal policy by the management

Statement	SD	D	M	A	SA
There is an effective and efficient administration of performance appraisal policy by the management	22 (8.8)	33 (13.2)	62 (24.8)	104 (41.6)	29 (11.6)

SD- Strongly disagree, D-Disagree, M-Moderate, A-Agree, SA- Strongly agree

From the above table, it is observed that 53.2% respondents agreed that there is an effective and efficient administration of performance appraisal policy by the management, 24.8% respondents are moderate and 22% respondents are disagreed.

Table 4.5: Summary of the statistics related to policy shared with staff

Statement	Yes	No
Is the policy shared with staff?	126 (50.4)	124 (49.6)

From above table it is observed that, 50.4% respondents agreed that policy shared with the staff and 49.6% respondents denied with the statement.

Table 4.6: Summary of the statistics related to appraised any staff

Statement	Yes	No
Have you appraised any staff?	102 (40.8)	148 (59.2)

From above table it is observed that, 40.8% respondents agreed that organisation appraised staff and 59.2% respondents denied with the statement.

Table 4.7: Summary of the statistics related to training on Performance Appraisal in the organization

Statement	Yes	No
Have you ever attended training on Performance Appraisal in the organization?	107 (42.8)	143 (57.2)

From above table it is observed that, 42.8% respondents agreed that they attended training on performance appraisal in the organization and 57.2% respondents denied with the statement.

4.3.3 Statistics related to fairness of performance appraisal system

In this section, statistics related to fairness of performance appraisal has been discussed.

Table 4.8: Summary of the statistics related to fairness of performance appraisal system

Statement	Yes	No
Have you ever been appraised on	131	119

performance while in this organization?	(52.4)	(47.6)
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From above table it is observed that, 52.4% respondents agreed that they been appraised on performance while in this organization and 47.6% respondents denied with the statement.

Table 4.9: Summary of the statistics related to performance appraisal form used by employees at the same grade/group

Statement	Yes	No
Is the same performance appraisal form used by employees at the same grade/group?	134 (53.6)	116 (46.4)

From above table it is observed that, 53.6% respondents agreed that same performance appraisal form used by employees at the same grade/group and 46.4% respondents denied with the statement.

Table 4.10: Summary of the statistics related to appraised done

Variable	N	%
Immediate Supervisor	33	13.2
Peer Colleague	29	11.6
Meeting between staff and immediate supervisor	80	32.0
Myself	91	36.4
Above all	17	6.8

From above table it is observed that, 13.2% respondents agreed that immediate supervisor, 11.6% agreed that peer colleague, 32% agreed that meeting between staff and immediate supervisor, 36.4% agreed that myself and 6.8% agreed above all.

Table 4.11: Summary of the statistics related to conduction of appraisal

Variable	N	%
With an appraisal form	60	24
Orally without documentation	104	41.6
Both orally and with appraisal form	86	34.4

From above table it is observed that, 24% respondents agreed that appraisal was conducted with an appraisal form, 41.6% agreed that appraisal was conducted with orally without documentation, 34.4% agreed that appraisal was conducted both orally and with appraisal form.

Table 4.12: Summary of the statistics related to pre-determined objectives against which you were evaluated

Statement	Yes	No
Were there pre-determined objectives against which you were evaluated?	133 (53.2)	117 (46.8)

From above table it is observed that, 53.2% respondents agreed that pre-determined objectives against which you were evaluated and 46.8% respondents denied with the statement.

Table 4.13: Summary of the statistics related to determination the objectives

Variable	N	%
Supervisor	56	22.4
Employee	58	23.2
Both supervisor and employee	66	26.4
I don't know	70	28

From above table it is observed that, 22.4% respondents agreed that objectives are determined by supervisor, 23.2% respondents agreed that objectives are determined by employee, 26.4% respondents agreed that objectives are determined by both supervisor and employee, and 28% respondents don't know.

Table 4.14: Summary of the statistics related to frequency of appraised

Variable	N	%
Every three months	23	9.2
Every six months	27	10.8
Every Year	94	37.6
Not determined	88	35.2

I don't know	18	7.2
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From above table it is observed that, 23% respondents agreed that frequency of appraisal is every three months, 10.8% respondents agreed that frequency of appraisal is every six months, 37.6% respondents agreed that frequency of appraisal is every year, 35.2% respondents agreed that frequency of appraisal is not determined and 7.2% respondents don't know,

Table 4.15: Summary of the statistics related to PA fairly conducted

Statement	Yes	No
In your view, was PA fairly conducted?	149 (59.6)	101 (40.4)

From above table it is observed that, 59.6% respondents agreed that PA was fairly conducted and 40.4% respondents denied with the statement.

Table 4.16: Summary of the statistics related to motivation by PA

Statement	Yes	No
Did you feel motivated by the PA process?	108 (43.2)	142 (56.8)

From above table it is observed that, 43.2% respondents agreed that they feel motivated by PA was fairly conducted and 56.8% respondents denied with the statement.

4.3.4 Statistics related to feedback of performance appraisal

In this section, statistics related to feedback of performance appraisal has been discussed.

Table 4.17: Summary of the statistics related to getting feedback after appraisal

Statement	Yes	No
Did you get feedback after appraisal?	138 (55.2)	112 (44.8)

From above table it is observed that, 55.2% respondents agreed that they get feedback after PA was fairly conducted and 44.8% respondents denied with the statement.

Table 4.18: Summary of the statistics related to feedback reflected performance

Statement	Yes	No
Do you think the feedback reflected your performance?	97 (38.8)	153 (61.2)

From above table it is observed that, 38.8% respondents agreed that they get feedback reflected their performance and 61.2% respondents denied with the statement.

Table 4.19: Summary of the statistics related to feedback received motivate them

Variable	N	%
Great extent	35	14
Somewhat	56	22.4
Very little	76	30.4
Not at all	83	33.2

From above table it is observed that, 14% respondents agreed that feedback received motivate them to great extent, 22.4% respondents agreed that feedback received motivate them somewhat, 30.4% respondents agreed that feedback received motivate them very little and 33.2% respondents agreed that not at all.

4.3.5 Statistics related to use of performance appraisal results

Table 4.20: Summary of the statistics related to organization use performance appraisal results

Statement	Yes	No
Does your organization use performance appraisal results?	120 (48)	130 (52)

From above table it is observed that, 48% respondents agreed that organization use performance appraisal results and 52% respondents denied with the statement.

Table 4.21: Summary of the statistics related to use of performance appraisal

Variable	N	%
For training needs assessment	70	28
To reward best performers	69	27.6
For promotion/demotions	70	28
Don't Know	41	16.4

From above table it is observed that, 28% respondents agreed that organization use performance appraisal for training needs assessment, 27.6% respondents agreed that

organization use performance appraisal to reward best performers, 28% respondents agreed that organization use performance appraisal for promotion/demotions, and 16.4% respondents don't know,

Table 4.22: Summary of the statistics related to use of performance appraisal is sufficient

Statement	Yes	No
Use of performance appraisal is sufficient	144 (57.6)	106 (42.4)

From above table it is observed that, 57.6% respondents agreed that use is sufficient and 42.4% respondents denied with the statement.

4.3.6 Statistics related to effect of performance appraisal on motivation

Table 4.23: Summary of the statistics related to effect of performance appraisal on motivation

Effect of performance appraisal on employee motivation	SD	D	M	A	SA
a. Performance appraisal is a critical component in the organization	19 (7.6)	30 (12)	15 (6)	85 (34)	101 (40.4)
b. Performance appraisal is based on my roles as an employee	15 (6)	32 (12.8)	73 (29.2)	103 (41.2)	27 (10.8)
c. There are pre-determined objectives for my evaluation	29 (11.6)	28 (11.2)	74 (29.6)	100 (40)	19 (7.6)
d. The most recent ratings I received are based on my work	27 (20.8)	47 (18.8)	10 (4)	96 (38.4)	70 (28)
e. I am motivated with the way performance appraisal is used to evaluate my performance.	19 (7.6)	19 (7.6)	89 (35.6)	95 (38)	28 (11.2)
f. I clearly understand the purpose of performance appraisal process	23 (9.2)	28 (11.2)	20 (8)	102 (40.8)	77 (30.8)
g. The process of staff performance appraisal in the organization is fairly conducted	17 (6.8)	32 (12.8)	22 (8.8)	106 (42.4)	73 (29.2)
h. Performance appraisal process motivates me as an employee of this organization	31 (12.4)	30 (12)	16 (6.4)	96 (38.4)	77 (30.8)
i. Performance appraisal has helped improve my job performance	25 (10)	32 (32.8)	18 (7.2)	83 (33.2)	92 (36.8)
j. I am satisfied with the way performance appraisal system is used to set my performance goals for each performance period.	27 (10.8)	32 (12.8)	14 (5.6)	80 (32)	97 (38.8)

4.4 The Proposed Research Model

The conceptual model of this study is developed based on variables that influence the performance appraisal on employee motivation in media and entertainment sector. The proposed research model consists of one dimension (performance appraisal) that lay an impact on the employee motivation as illustrated in figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1 Research Model

4.5 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Schreiber, Stage and King, (2006) stated that “Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is a theory driven confirmatory statistical technique”. CFA is a part of structural equation modelling (SEM). It used to verify the relationship between latent variables and their indicators (Suhr, 2006). Theoretical knowledge or empirical research or both are applied together to postulate prior relationship patterns in a research model and then tests the hypotheses statistically.

The independent variables are unobserved constructs, also known as factors, dimensions or latent variables. CFA is a way to specify which variables load onto which factors. Unlike exploratory factor analysis (EFA), the researcher must specify all the aspects of the CFA model in advance (Brown, 2006). In addition to EFA, CFA provides many analytical possibilities that are not possible with regard to EFA.

Model Specification: Before indulging in any analysis regarding the research model, the researcher first sets the assumed relationships between the different factors considered in the study and conceptualises a theoretical model based on the past theories, conceptual and empirical research, and results.

Model Identification: It is highly critical to identify whether the model is over-identified, just identified or under-identified. Whenever the amount of data points was equal to estimated parameter otherwise the model is “just-identified”. This aligns well with the data. If less than the estimated parameter is available, then the model is "under identified." Unable to

estimate the parameter in the scenario. The researcher then deletes some of the parameters calculated. The 'over-identified' model & analysis

The independent variables are unobserved constructs, also known as factors, dimensions or latent variables. CFA is a way to specify which variables load onto which factors. Unlike exploratory factor analysis (EFA), the researcher must specify all the aspects of the CFA model in advance (Brown, 2006). In addition to EFA, CFA provides many analytical possibilities that are not possible with regard to EFA.

Model Estimation: There are several estimate techniques available in SEMs such as ML, GLS, weighted least squares, partial least squares (PLS). The most used maximum probability estimate was MLE (Albright and Park, 2009). Thus, MLE approach in PLS-SEM has been used in the present work to assess the fit measures.

Model Evaluation: Brown, (2006) stated that “CFA does not calculate factor scores like EFA, rather it provides many goodness-of-fit measures to evaluate the model”. After obtaining the parameter estimation values, model fit is evaluated and compared with the recommended fit indices (Marsh, Hau and Wen, 2004; Hu and Bentler, 1998; Prudon, 2013 and Hair et al., 2006).

Table 4.24: Model Fitness Criteria

Fit index	Threshold Levels	Sources
Chi-Square χ^2	Lower χ^2 relative to df 2:1	Moss, 2016; Marsh et al., 2004; Prudon, 2013
Normed χ^2 (χ^2/ df) (CMIN)	3.1	Bagozzi et al. 1998; Kline, 1998; Schumacker and Lomax, 2004
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	≥ 0.80	Joreskog and Sorbom, 1989
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	≥ 0.80	Hair et al., 2006
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	< 0.06	Browne and Cudeck, 1993
Standardised Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)	< 0.08	Browne and Cudeck, 1993
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	≥ 0.90	Byrne, 2001
Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)	≥ 0.80	Hooper et al., 2008
Parsimony Normed Fit Index (PNFI)	No threshold levels	Kenny, 2015
Standardised Residuals	< 2.58	Joreskog and Sorbom, 1989
PClose	> 0.05	Hu and Bentler, 1999

According to Yuan, (2005) *“For CFA and SEM, it is imperative to examine whether the specified theoretical model fits the data”*. For model fitness, it is not mandatory to include every index represented in the PLS-SEM output. Markland, (2007) and Goffin, (2007) stated that *“there are no golden rules for evaluating the model fitness because different measurement indices indicate different aspects of the model fit, thus reporting a variety of indices is significant”*. According to Chen, Curran, Bollen, Kirby and Paxton, (2008); Marsh et al., (2004); Hu and Bentler, (1998); Miles and Shevlin, (2007) and Prudon, (2013) *“the mostly commonly reported fit indices are the CFI, GFI, NFI, NNFI and the chi-square value along with its degrees of freedom and associated p-value should be reported at all times”*. Saris, Satorra and Veld (2009) suggested that *“it is sensible to report the chi-square value, its degrees of freedom, p-value, the RMSEA and its associated confidence interval, the SRMR, the CFI and one parsimony fit index such as PNFI”*. These model fitness indices have been selected, over others since they were emerged as most unaffected to sample size, model misspecification and parameter estimation (Hooper, Coughlan and Mullen, 2008).

Thus, for the purpose of evaluating the research model on the basis of CFA and SEM, it was decided to report the following goodness of fit indices: chi square and the degrees of freedom, normed chi-square, RMSEA, SRMR, GFI, AGFI, CGI, NNFI and PNFI in this study.

The proposed research model presents the influence of social media efforts on brand equity and purchase intention. Model fitness have been discussed as below:

a) The Absolute Fit Indices: Hooper et al., (2008) stated that *“Absolute fit Indices provide the most fundamental indicator for model fit measure which includes Chi Squared test, AGFI, GFI, SRMR, and RMSEA.*

Chi-square χ^2 : χ^2 tests the hypothesis that there is a discrepancy between model-implied covariance matrix and original covariance matrix. It is a statistical fit index and, in this study its value is within the range.

RMSEA: Cangur et al., (2015) stated that *“RMSEA is an index of the difference between the observed covariance matrix per degree of freedom and the hypothesized covariance matrix that denotes the model”*. Zero represents a perfect fit, and higher values indicate lack of fit. Hu and Bentler, 1999 suggested an acceptable range of RMSEA value of 0.06 or less which was in range in this study as shown in table 4.28.

SRMR: Chen, (2007) stated that *“Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) is an index of the average of standardized residuals between the observed and the hypothesized*

covariance matrices”. SRMR value for the research model was within the acceptable range as shown in table 4.28.

Goodness of Fit Index (GFI): The goodness of fit index (GFI) is a measure of fit between the hypothesized model and the observed covariance matrix. GFI value for the research model was within the acceptable range as shown in table 4.28.

Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI): It corrects the GFI, which is affected by the number of indicators of each latent variable. AGFI value for the research model was within the acceptable range as shown in table 4.28.

b) Normed Chi-Square: The minimal difference between both (chi-square index) is the degree of freedom (χ^2/ df). It is also the minimum difference. The indices are less sensitive to the sample size. Acceptance criteria vary from 2 to 5. (Ullman, 2006). The value for Normed Chi-Square in the research model was within the acceptable range as shown in table 4.28.

c) The Relative/Incremental/ Comparative Fit Indices: They rely on comparison with a baseline model unlike the absolute fit indices, which measure how well the model fits the data (Joreskog and Sorbom, 1993). These include CFI, NFI and NNFI.

Comparative Fit Index: CFI refers to amount of variance accounted in a covariance matrix. Its ranges from 0 to 1. A higher CFI indicates better fit. In short, the CFI should be close to 0.95 or higher (Fan et al. 1999). The value for CFI in the research model was within the acceptable range as shown in table 4.28.

Normed Fit Index: It is a measure of goodness of fit which is not affected by number of variables in model. Its value ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 is ideal. It the difference between the chi-square of the null model and the chi square of target model, divided by the chi-square of the null model. The value for NFI in the research model was within the acceptable range as shown in table 4.28.

Tucker-Lewis Index or Non-Normed Fit Index: TLI is a non-normed fit index that overcomes the disadvantages of NFI. According to Marsh, Balla, and McDonald (1988), the “*TLI is relatively independent of sample size values over .90 or over .95 are considered acceptable for TLI*”. The value for NNFI in the research model was within the acceptable range as shown in table 4.28.

d) Parsimony Fit Indices: Mulaik, James, Alstine, Bennet, Lind and Stilwell (1989) The Parsimony Goodness-of-Fit Index (PGFI) as well as the Parsimonious Standard Fit Index were created two parsimony index fit: (PNFI). By correcting the loss of freedom, the PGFI is built upon the GFI. The PNFI likewise adapts to freedom levels, even though it is based mostly on NFI (Mulaik et al. 1989). However, Mulaik et al (1989) indicate that now the

parsimony fit indices in the 0.50 range cannot be obtained whereas other fit index qualities acquire values over 0.90 (See Table 4.28).

e) PClose (p of close fit): This measures the unilateral test of null hypothesis: the RMSEA was equal to 0.05, which is known as just a model of closure (Kenny, 2014). There is few specifying errors in such a model. The other one-sided assumption is the RMSEA is larger than 0.05. Thus, if the p is larger than .05 (that is just not statistically significant), the fit of a model is "close." Unless the p is lower than .05, the fitting of the model is fit (i.e., the RMSEA is greater than 0.05) (See Table 4.28).

Table 4.25: Summary of the Model Fit Indices for the Structural Model (SEM)

Fit index	Observed levels	Threshold Levels	Model fit
Chi-Square χ^2	641.875	Lower χ^2 relative to df 2:1	Acceptable
Normed χ^2 (χ^2 / df) (CMIN)	1.472	3:1	Acceptable
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	0.834	≥ 0.80	Acceptable
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	0.828	≥ 0.80	Acceptable
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	0.048	< 0.06	Acceptable
Standardised Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)	0.066	< 0.08	Acceptable
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.903	≥ 0.90	Acceptable
Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)	0.845	≥ 0.80	Acceptable
Parsimony Normed Fit Index (PNFI)	0.689	No threshold levels	Acceptable
Standardised Residuals	1.162	< 2.58	Acceptable
PClose	0.218	> 0.05	Acceptable

4.6 Reliability analysis

According to Webb, Shavelson and Haertel (2007) “Reliability refers to the precision or consistency of measurement; that is, the overall proportion of true score variance to total observed variance of the measure”. Straub, (1989) stated that “Reliability refers to the degree

to which a scale yields consistent and stable measures over time and applies only to reflective indicators”. According to Chin (1998b), the reliability level above 0.7 ensures that the scale is reliable which is the case for all constructs in this study (Please see table 4.29). In this study, reliability was assessed using two ways: Cronbach alpha and Composite or construct reliability.

Reliability Test Using Cronbach Alpha: Cronbach (1951) proposed a way to measure reliability of a construct. Cronbach’s alpha is generally used as a measure of scale reliability (Hair et al., 2006). Cronbach alpha was calculated for assessing the reliability of the research instrument in this study (Cronbach, 1951). It measures the internal consistency of the items. Cronbach alpha was computed separately for the different dimensions undertaken in this study. Hair et al., (2006) recommended the value of Cronbach’s alpha should be more or equal 0.7 or more and it has been used as a criterion for the scale to be reliable. This study assesses the reliability of instrument with Cronbach’s alpha. It was found that all the dimensions depicted the Cronbach’s alpha value greater than 0.7, thereby confirming that the research instrument is reliable. Apart from Cronbach Alpha, composite reliability was also measured in this study.

Table 4.26: Reliability Analysis Pertaining to Variables

S.no	Variables	Value of Cronbach Alpha Coefficient	CR
1	Setting work related goals (SWRG)	0.861	0.862
2	Employee Participation (EP)	0.774	0.781
3	Fairness in the process (FIP)	0.836	0.837
4	Usage of results (UOR)	0.737	0.812
5	Timely feedback (TF)	0.714	0.764
6	Initiative (INT)	0.788	0.789
7	Problem solving (PS)	0.833	0.728
8	Team work (TW)	0.744	0.740
9	Enthusiastic employees (EM)	0.789	0.791
10	Quality of work (QOW)	0.718	0.834

Construct or Composite Reliability (C.R.): After establishing the unidimensionality of the scale, an assessment of the statistical reliability is imperative before performing any further validation analysis (Anderson and Gerbing, 1991). Reliability assures the consistency and dependability of the scale (Gatewood and Field, 1990). Composite reliability (CR) refers to a measurement of internal consistency in a scale. If a scale has a value of C.R. for all the dimensions above 0.7, it is reliable (Hair et al., 2006). In this study, C.R. for all the variables

considered in the research model was found to be greater than 0.70 as illustrated in table 4.30. Thus, the research instrument developed was reliable.

4.7 Validity Analysis

According to Brown, (1996) the common concept of validity was defined as "the degree to which a test measures what it claims, or purports, to be measuring". Malhotra, (2003) and Zikmund, (2003) stated that validity refers to "the extent to which differences in observed scale scores reflect true differences among objects on the characteristic being measured, rather than systematic or random error". Most of the time validity is assessed by the inter correlation between set of variables (Hair et al., 2006). It really is examined if the constructive measures are meant to measure and divide them in convergent and discriminate validity through making sure a concept is valid (Cronbach and Meehl, 1955). There are three types of widely accepted validity: convergent, Discriminant and nomological (Zait and Berteau, 2011; Hair et al., 2006 and Trochim, 2006). Convergent and discriminant validity constitute construct validity.

Content Validity: Content validity concerns the extent to which a scale measures relevant aspects of the construct (latent variable) under the investigation (Zikmund, 2000). The content validity of the constructs used in this research study was achieved by employing the pre - existing measurements that have been previously used by many researchers. Content validity of the variables used in the research study was made by seeking the approval from the research supervisor, members of doctoral committee and doing pre - test with 100 respondents chosen randomly in India. The research supervisor and members of doctoral committee approved the scales used pertaining to the variables of the research study. They felt that the statements used in the scales pertaining to variables of the research study measured the same. It was supported by the results of the pilot study with respondents in India which indicated that most of the respondents stated that statements in the scales pertaining to the variables of the research study were understandable and comprehensive.

Correlational or Convergent Validity: To confirm the validity of the construct, Correlational analysis was performed. It empirically assesses how the variables are inter-correlated. A construct is indeed an attribute, aptitude or capacity in the human brain that is also characterized with accepted concepts. The validity of the building has been described as that of the experimental proof that now the test evaluates its building (Shiken, 2000). Individual items were checked to check if it is the same element closely (Hair et al., 2006). In this study,

inter-item correlation values higher than 0.30 was found except for few inter-item correlation values which are satisfactory. Item-total correlation values of the indicators in each construct were above 0.3 as shown in table 4.12. Cohen (1998) suggested that “correlations $r=0.10$ to 0.29 indicate small correlation, $r=0.30$ to 0.49 indicate medium correlation and $r=0.50$ to 1.0 indicate a large correlation”. These results suggest that the scale possesses convergent validity.

Discriminant Validity: Discriminant validity measures when unrelated objects are actually not linked (Lange et al., 2014). The discriminating validity is guaranteed as per Gefen and Straub (2005), when square roots of the AVE were higher than the relationship between structures in the same row and column, but so is the case for any and all builds. Average Variance Extracted the PLS-SEM package is computed. The findings in table 4.12 depict that the square roots of AVEs was higher than the correlations between constructs / variables. These results confirmed discriminant validity possessed by scale.

Reliability and validity are closely related to each other (Bollen, 1989). A measure can be reliable but not valid or a measure can be valid but reliable. Hence reliability and validity are both needed to measure the adequacy of construct (Holmes-Smith Cunningham and Coote, 2006). So, in present study 39 items of the questionnaire were proved as a reliable and valid research instrument.

Table 4.27: Measurement model output-CFA

	Dimensions	Loadings	t-value	AVE
PA	SWRG	0.928	24.529	0.555
	EP	0.789	34.302	0.531
	FIP	0.921	15.839	0.563
	UOR	0.861	8.877	0.523
	TF	0.910	8.399	0.516
EM	INT	0.782	9.948	0.507
	PS	0.861	9.387	0.523
	TW	0.898	12.558	0.516
	EE	0.841	9.942	0.501
	QOW	0.837	10.323	0.512

Thus, measurement model has been assessed by values of composite reliability; convergent validity; discriminant validity and indicator loadings. These values were found within the specified limits (Hair et al., 2013).

Table 4.28: Comparative Fit Index (CFI)

Dimension	CFI
PA	0.930
EM	0.939

We focused on the CFI because it is a fit index that also performs well in small sample (Hu and Bentler, 1999). A CFI value of 0.95 suggests a good fit of the model to the data (Hu and Bentler, 1999), a CFI between 0.90 and 0.95 corresponds to a reasonable fit (Bentler, 1990; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2005), and a CFI value lower than 0.90 indicates a bad fit (Bentler, 1990). CFI of constructs are above the acceptable range. Furthermore, the existence of discriminant validity was shown in the model. According to Fornell and Larcker [80] and Roldán and Sánchez-Franco [82], to guarantee the discriminant validity, the square root of the AVE measures must be superior to all the correlations among all the constructs.

Table 4.29: Table showing the Square Root of AVE and Correlation Coefficient Values

	SWRG	EP	FIP	UOR	TF	INT	PS	TW	EE	QOW
SWRG	.712									
EP	.594	.711								
FIP	.558	.532	.718							
UOR	.582	.534	.686	.708						
TF	.637	.502	.533	.669	.714					
INT	.579	.601	.711	.521	.611	.713				
PS	.614	.523	.566	.527	.709	.674	.705			
TW	.530	.629	.579	.553	.665	.628	.612	.709		
EE	.671	.648	.635	.676	.693	.571	.623	.642	.706	
QOW	.501	.489	.567	.689	.544	.579	.558	.572	.613	.712

Above Table shows, the square root of the AVE (main diagonal) is in all cases superior to the correlations among the constructs, which shows discriminant validity.

4.8. Hypotheses Testing

PLS-SEM has been used to do the data analysis. Smart PLS 3 was used to do the analysis (Ringle et al., 2015). Because linear regressions, correlations, and variances analysis can only look at a complicated model in masses, they are not very useful (Lowry and Gaskin, 2014). To further comprehend the link between the indicators and the latent variable, a reflective model was developed.

Figure 4.2 SEM output

H1: There is a significant impact of performance appraisal on employee motivation

To test the hypothesis, PLS-SEM was used. Results indicate that beta value is 0.832 and p value is 0.000 which is significant (See Table 4.30). Thus null hypothesis rejected and concluded that there is a significant impact of performance appraisal on employee motivation.

Table 4.30: SEM results

Hypotheses	Path	Path coefficient	Standard deviation	t-static	Decision
H ₁	PA → EM	0.832	0.064	16.553	Supported

H2. There is a significant impact of fairness of performance appraisal system

To study the impact of fairness of performance appraisal system, Regression is applied.

Table 4.31: Model summary

Model	Model summary				
	R	Rsq.	Radj.	SE	DW
1	.794 ^a	0.631	0.625	0.45826	1.941

Table 4.32: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	185.407	2	20.601	8.097	.000 ^b
Residual	108.362	248	0.210		
Total	293.770	249			

Table 4.33: Regression

Variable	Coefficients		
	β	t	p
Fairness of performance appraisal system	0.176	12.589	0.001

Results indicate that beta value is 0.176 and p value is 0.000 which is significant (See Table 4.33). Thus null hypothesis rejected and concluded that there is a significant impact of fairness of performance appraisal system.

H3. There is a significant impact of feedback on performance appraisal

To study the impact of impact of feedback on performance appraisal, Regression is applied.

Table 4.34: Model summary

Model summary					
Model	R	Rsqu.	Radj.	SE	DW
1	.741 ^a	0.676	0.585	0.4787	1.939

Table 4.35: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	115.27	2	115.27	6.131	.000 ^b
Residual	98.62	248	0.210		
Total	213.89	249			

Table 4.36: Regression

Variable	Coefficients		
	β	t	p
Feedback on performance appraisal	0.232	17.312	0.001

Results indicate that beta value is 0.232 and p value is 0.000 which is significant (See Table 4.36). Thus null hypothesis rejected and concluded that there is a significant impact of fairness of performance appraisal system.

H4. There is a significant impact of use of performance appraisal results on employee motivation

To study the impact of impact of use of performance appraisal results, Regression is applied.

Table 4.37: Model summary

Model summary					
Model	R	Rsq.	Radj.	SE	DW
1	.738 ^a	0.682	0.638	0.8767	1.921

Table 4.38: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	121.45	2	121.45	8.414	.000 ^b
Residual	110.21	248	0.210		
Total	231.66	249			

Table 4.39: Regression

Variable	Coefficients		
	β	t	p
Use of performance appraisal results	0.191	10.288	0.001

Results indicate that beta value is 0.191 and p value is 0.000 which is significant (See Table 4.36). Thus null hypothesis rejected and concluded that there is a significant impact of use of performance appraisal results on employee motivation.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

- On the basis of gender distribution, 55.2% are male and 44.8% are female. According to age, 34% belongs to age group of 18-35 years, 23.2% belongs to age group of 36-45 years, 23.6% belongs to age group of 46-55 years, and 19.2% belongs to age group of above 55 years. On the basis of educational qualification, 46.4% respondents are graduated, 36.8% respondents are post graduated and 16.8% respondents have professional degree. On the basis of job position, 10.4% respondents are senior manager, 54.8% respondents are middle manager and 34.8% respondents are operational staff. On the basis of working in organisation, 23.6% respondents are working below year, 26.4% respondents are working from 4-6 years, 21.6% respondents are working from 7-9 years, and 17.6% respondents are working from 10 years and above.
- It is observed that, 55.2% respondents agreed that organization have a performance appraisal policy and 44.2% respondents denied with the statement. It is observed that 104% respondents agreed that there is an effective and efficient administration of performance appraisal policy by the management, 24.8% respondents are moderate and 13.2% respondents are disagreed. It is observed that, 50.4% respondents agreed that policy shared with the staff and 49.6% respondents denied with the statement. 40.8% respondents agreed that organisation appraised staff and 59.2% respondents denied with the statement. 42.8% respondents agreed that they attended training on performance appraisal in the organization and 57.2% respondents denied with the statement.
- 52.4% respondents agreed that they been appraised on performance while in this organization and 47.6% respondents denied with the statement. 53.6% respondents agreed that same performance appraisal form used by employees at the same grade/group and 46.4% respondents denied with the statement. 13.2% respondents agreed that immediate supervisor, 11.6% agreed that peer colleague, 32% agreed that

meeting between staff and immediate supervisor, 36.4% agreed that myself and 6.8% agreed above all. 24% respondents agreed that appraisal was conducted with an appraisal form, 41.6% agreed that appraisal was conducted with orally without documentation, 34.4% agreed that appraisal was conducted both orally and with appraisal form.

- 53.2% respondents agreed that pre-determined objectives against which you were evaluated and 46.8% respondents denied with the statement. It is observed that, 22.4% respondents agreed that objectives are determined by supervisor, 23.2% respondents agreed that objectives are determined by employee, 26.4% respondents agreed that objectives are determined by both supervisor and employee, and 28% respondents don't know.
- 23% respondents agreed that frequency of appraisal is every three months, 10.8% respondents agreed that frequency of appraisal is every six months, 37.6% respondents agreed that frequency of appraisal is every year, 35.2% respondents agreed that frequency of appraisal is not determined and 7.2% respondents don't know. 59.6% respondents agreed that PA was fairly conducted and 40.4% respondents denied with the statement. 43.2% respondents agreed that they feel motivated by PA was fairly conducted and 56.8% respondents denied with the statement.
- 55.2% respondents agreed that they get feedback after PA was fairly conducted and 44.8% respondents denied with the statement. 38.8% respondents agreed that they get feedback reflected their performance and 61.2% respondents denied with the statement. 14% respondents agreed that feedback received motivate them to great extent, 22.4% respondents agreed that feedback received motivate them somewhat, 30.4% respondents agreed that feedback received motivate them very little and 33.2% respondents agreed that not at all.
- 48% respondents agreed that organization use performance appraisal results and 52% respondents denied with the statement. It is observed that, 28% respondents agreed that organization use performance appraisal for training needs assessment, 27.6% respondents agreed that organization use performance appraisal to reward best performers, 28% respondents agreed that organization use performance appraisal for promotion/demotions, and 16.4% respondents don't know. It is observed that, 57.6% respondents agreed that use is sufficient and 42.4% respondents denied with the statement.

- PLS-SEM has been used to do the data analysis and hypothesis testing of main variables. To test the hypothesis, PLS-SEM was used. Results indicate that beta value is 0.832 and p value is 0.000 which is significant. Thus null hypothesis rejected and concluded that there is a significant impact of performance appraisal on employee motivation.
- To study the impact of fairness of performance appraisal system, Regression is applied. Results indicate that beta value is 0.176 and p value is 0.000 which is significant. Thus null hypothesis rejected and concluded that there is a significant impact of fairness of performance appraisal system. To study the impact of impact of feedback on performance appraisal, Regression is applied. Results indicate that beta value is 0.232 and p value is 0.000 which is significant. Thus null hypothesis rejected and concluded that there is a significant impact of fairness of performance appraisal system. To study the impact of impact of use of performance appraisal results, Regression is applied. Results indicate that beta value is 0.191 and p value is 0.000 which is significant. Thus null hypothesis rejected and concluded that there is a significant impact of use of performance appraisal results on employee motivation.

Conclusion

Human resource management is a function in organizations designed to maximize employee performance towards employer's strategic objectives. Human resource and management partnership is unique in healthcare industry because many healthcare organizations have a dual administrative structure of clinical managers and health service managers that supervise two distinct group of employees with different responsibilities and training needs. The goal of healthcare industry is to provide highest quality of patient care. The employee performance appraisal is an important career development tool for the manager and employee. The manager can help guide the employee on the path to corporate advancement, and the employee gets a clearer understanding of what is expected from their daily job duties. The underlying objective of PA, is to improve the performance of the individual employee, thereby leading to improvement in the performance of the organization as a whole. PA is one of the rangesof tools that can be used to manage performance effectively in that it provides data which feeds into other elements of the performance management process. Performance appraisals have a wide variety of effects on employees that managers must identify and understand. Performance appraisals are also crucial for career and succession development.

Performance review designed for workforce inspiration, position and conduct improvement, converse directorial aims, along with nurturing optimistic associations between supervision and workforce. Performance evaluation ought to be treated as an enduring developmental progression to a certain extent than a prescribed once-a-year review. It ought to be intimately monitored by both worker and assessor to guarantee that targets are mortal achieved. By preparing physically conscientiously and signifying a keenness to work together with your reviewer to enlarge your responsibility, you will craft an encouraging consciousness. Worker act, in common, submit to behavior with the intention of applicable to directorial goals and with the intention to organize entity workforce.

Motivation is an important subject area for researchers and practitioners of management all over the world. Motivation is equally relevant to public and private sectors and civil and military establishments. An employee performance appraisal can act as motivation for an employee to improve his productivity. When an employee sees his goals clearly defined, his performance challenges identified and career development solutions in place to help advance his career, the effect is to motivate the employee to achieve those goals. Creating a comprehensive plan for employee development and giving an employee achievement to strive for will inspire a higher level of efficiency. Once employee performance is measured against the set goals and objectives, a need can be identified about the future strategies of employee motivation. The basic purpose of an appraisal system should be to improve the employee performance that will leads towards the organization success.

Policy recommendations

1. Every organisation should have a performance appraisal policy and policy statement must be properly communicated to the employees in the induction programme of the company.
2. A well understanding of performance appraisal system is essential for the success of the process. So frequent performance appraisal training is mandatory in every organisation.
3. Each organisations conducting PA in different time intervals and using their own methods. The employees must have a clear idea about the methods and process of PA.
4. PA must be conducted fairly and openly.

5. PA feedback is an essential component of every PA system. So after the evaluation the results and modifications must be properly communicated to the employees. This leads to better performance in future period.
6. Each and every employee must know the results of PA. So the employer must disclose the PA results properly to its employees.
7. The results of performance appraisal must be rewarded either in terms of promotion or in terms of monetary rewards. Sometimes it is mandatory to provide training to under performers. Then only the organisation will enhance the organisational efficiency.
8. Performance appraisal has a significant impact on employee motivation. So the entire process of the PA is vital. If the organisation fails to conduct PA system properly it will leads to greater dissatisfaction. As a device to enhance employee performance, PA is commonly acts a motivational tool.

Future enactment

The current research study offers the following suggestions for future research:

- This research was limited to the media and entertainment sector. To understand how PA methods are used in various industries, such as the industrial, agricultural, and allied sectors, as well as other service sector units, it is required to conduct a thorough investigation.
- Another area for research is the requirement for new PA models and procedures in the modern business world. The current appraisal techniques are not always adequate. Therefore, in a rapidly evolving technology environment, a new scientific model is crucial for assessing employee performance. Future studies should also focus on developing new techniques.
- In Kerala, there haven't been any studies specifically on PA in public sector businesses. Numerous studies already conducted have found that businesses in the private sector carry out PA more successfully than those in the public sector. As a result, the field is lacking.
- Different methods of appraisal are used by the various industries. The methods or procedures of PA utilised by different industries differ significantly in some ways. Finding the best practises for applying PA in various businesses can be done through a comparative study.

- This study has limited to motivation and PA. However, PA has a direct or indirect relationship with a number of other factors, including pay and benefits, incentives, promotions, employee happiness, productivity, training, managerial choices, etc.

Dr. Sujith AS - A brief Biography

Dr. Sujith AS got a Master's degree in human resource management from Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala and a Master's degree in Commerce from Madurai Kamaraj University, Tamil Nadu. In 2020, awarded Ph.D from Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala. In 2021, joined as a PDF in Commerce at Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka.

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